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Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance

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1 Migration to Austria: Statistics and data overview

1.1 Migrants in Austria: Short history and current developments¹

In the past decades, Austria has clearly turned into a country of immigration. Looking back briefly at the migration history after the Second World War, two groups of migrants have been of particular importance until the mid-1990s: 1) refugees from communist countries – until the end of the 1980s – and 2) labour migrants and their families. Due to the country's neutrality during the Cold War period, Austria received three major waves of refugees, namely from Hungary in 1956, from Czechoslovakia in 1968 and from Poland in 1981. However, for many of these refugees Austria was only a transit country on their way to other destinations. At the beginning of the 1960s, Austria saw a growing need for additional labour and actively started to recruit workers in Turkey (1964) and the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (1966). Contrary to what had originally been planned (namely the rotation model of 'guest workers'), many of the workers stayed and brought their families to Austria.

Since Austria's EU accession in 1995 and the accessions of mostly Eastern European countries in 2004 and 2007, intra-EU mobility has been gaining importance, most of all from the neighbouring countries of Germany, Slovakia and Hungary but also from Poland, Romania and Bulgaria. 46 per cent of the foreign-born population have immigrated from another EU/EEA² member state. Many of them came after the accessions but quite a few arrived already before these points in time. Either way, intra-EU mobility is not the focus of the present

¹ The general data situation on migration in Austria displays both positive and negative features. Statistics Austria (a federal institution under public law responsible for providing services in the area of federal statistics) collects data on the population via the Population Register, which is based on the obligatory registration of every person changing his/her main residence or entering/leaving Austria with the respective municipality. The data collected at registration include place of birth, sex, age and citizenship. This makes it possible to continuously check the stocks and flow of the population on all spatial levels. The Austrian Population Register follows the UN definitions for short-term and long-term migrants. One problem arises from the fact that migrants are more likely not to deregister when they leave Austria, which leads to the assumption that the statistical migration balance is probably higher than the actual migration balance (compare Reeger 2009: 116). Furthermore, these data do not include any information on the legal status of migrants. Data overviews on the structure of the population are published on the website of Statistics Austria. For an in-depth analysis access to data is fee-based. Statistics specifically on asylum are collected by the Federal Ministry of the Interior (BM.I) and published in monthly and annual reports on the ministry's webpage but only on the national level and not spatially disaggregated. This data collection includes asylum applications by sex and countries of origin as well as information on unaccompanied minors and statistics on negative and positive decisions by type of title. Regarding third country nationals in general, the BM.I also publishes 'Aliens, Settlement and Residence Statistics' on a monthly and yearly basis. These statistics include information on existing valid residence titles and newly granted residence titles by citizenship. All of these data sources are going to be used in the following outline on migrants in Austria, stocks and flows as well as the basic structural features of migration.

² Definition and clarification: Persons from the EEA and Switzerland enjoy freedom of movement and do not face barriers when accessing Austria. The EEA consists of all EU member states, Iceland,

report and the numbers are just shown in order to provide an overall picture of immigration to Austria and the current structure of the population (see Table 1).

Zooming in on third country nationals, migrants from former Yugoslavia and from Turkey, who arrived as ‘guest workers’ in the 1960s, and their descendants still form an important and growing foreign-born group in Austria, as the comparison between 2011 and 2017 shows.³ In total, more than half a million persons (almost one third of the foreign-born population and 58 per cent of those born in third countries) came from Turkey, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Kosovo and Macedonia. Furthermore, this migration flow continued when more than 100,000 refugees from these regions fled to Austria during the Balkan War in the 1990s.

Table 1: Austrian population by country of birth, 2011 and 2017

	2011 Abs.	2011 In %		2017 Abs.	2017 In %		Change 2011- 2017 in %
Total population	8,375,164	100.0		8,772,865	100.0		4.7
Austria	7,080,458	84.5		7,116,599	81.1		0.5
Abroad	1,294,706	15.5		1,656,266	18.9		27.9
EU and EFTA countries	585,276	7.0		755,824	8.6		29.1
Third countries	709,430	8.5	100.0	900,442	10.3	100.0	26.9
Europe, among these:	528,856	6.3	74.5	577,595	6.6	64.1	9.2
Bosnia and Herzegovina	149,679	1.8	21.1	164,291	1.9	18.2	9.8
Kosovo	27,135	0.3	3.8	31,809	0.4	3.5	17.2
Macedonia	21,134	0.3	3.0	25,117	0.3	2.8	18.8
Russian Federation	26,432	0.3	3.7	33,851	0.4	3.8	28.1
Serbia	130,931	1.6	18.5	139,137	1.6	15.5	6.3
Turkey	158,535	1.9	22.3	160,371	1.8	17.8	1.2
Africa	40,090	0.5	5.7	53,961	0.6	6.0	34.6
Asia, among these:	107,684	1.3	15.2	222,297	2.5	24.7	106.4
Afghanistan	8,428	0.1	1.2	44,684	0.5	5.0	430.2
Iraq	4,870	0.1	0.7	16,197	0.2	1.8	232.6
Syria	3,046	0.0	0.4	41,588	0.5	4.6	1265.3
America	29,783	0.4	4.2	36,233	0.4	4.0	21.7
other, unknown	3,017	0.0	0.4	10,356	0.1	1.2	243.3

Source: Statistics Austria, Population Register; own calculation.

The development between 2011 and 2017 has been positive for all groups under consideration, some only slightly (Austria +0.5%), some more pronounced. In terms of dynamics, the immigration of refugees from Afghanistan, Syria and Iraq is of crucial importance. While only

Liechtenstein and Norway. Persons from any other country are so-called ‘third country nationals’ and need a residence title if they intend to stay in Austria for more than six months.

³ Note: Countries under consideration in this group are the successor states of former Yugoslavia and Turkey. The following have been included: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Macedonia and Serbia. Croatia and Slovenia are now EU member states and are thus not counted in this group.

16,344 persons from these three countries resided in Austria in 2011, their number grew to 102,469 persons at the beginning of 2017.

Table 2: Current residence titles of third country nationals in Austria, 2016

	Men	Women	Total	In %	Women in %
Permanent Residence EU	131,303	125,547	256,850	56.5	48.9
Red-White-Red Card Plus	47,434	48,705	96,139	21.1	50.7
Family Members	16,100	22,898	38,998	8.6	58.9
Residence Permit	12,875	14,111	26,986	5.9	52.3
Permanent Residence Family Member	7,957	9,224	17,181	3.8	53.7
Former Settlement Certificate	5,141	4,694	9,835	2.2	47.7
Settlement Permit	2,608	4,226	6,834	1.5	61.8
Red-White-Red Card	1,151	522	1,673	0.4	31.2
EU Blue Card	196	96	292	0.1	32.3
Total	224,765	230,023	454,788	100.0	50.6

Source: Statistics by the BM.I; own calculation.

Basically, third country nationals (in this definition excluding asylum applicants and refugees, mainly those who come for work or education purposes or in order to reunite with their family) need a residence title, if they want to stay in Austria for a longer period of time or permanently. There is an abundance of different titles regarding, i. a., the length and purpose of stay (see Chapter 5.1 for a more detailed description). In 2016, there were almost 450,000 active residence titles. The most important category refers to 'permanent residence EU' (256,850 cases, 57% of all active titles) with an almost equal share of men and women (see Table 2). This title allows for an unlimited stay and access to the labour market and is available after five years of permanent residence in Austria. The Red-White-Red Card and Red-White-Red Card Plus, which were designed and implemented to attract skilled workers, made up 21.5% of the residence titles, and again there is an equal share of men and women in the quantitatively more important Red-White-Red Card Plus scheme. Other residence titles include those for family members and more temporary forms of permits.

Figure 1: Net migration for selected groups born in third countries, 2011-2016

Source: Statistics Austria, Population Register; own calculation.

Moving from stocks to flows, Figure 1 shows that the net migration from various regions outside of the EEA has been quite stable and consistently positive from 2011 until 2014, with European third countries dominating the scene. The year 2015 clearly was an exception, as we already mentioned above. Like other Western European countries, Austria witnessed a substantial inflow of refugees from Afghanistan, Syria and Iraq.

1.2 Refugees in Austria

In the next step, we will zoom in on the group of recent refugees. Contrary to the data from the Population Register displayed in Table 1 and Figure 1 that only contain the place of birth but not the legal status of immigrants, Table 3 reflects the developments as of 2011 from the perspective of Asylum Statistics. Again, the dynamics are striking. From 2011 until 2016 (the numbers for 2017 are not available yet), 208,021 persons from 142 countries applied for asylum in Austria. The three most important countries of origin are Afghanistan (around one quarter of all applications), Syria and Iraq. These three countries make up 56 per cent of all asylum applicants in this time period (see Table 3). Like many other EU countries, Austria has witnessed a peak inflow of refugees in 2015 with 88,340 applications compared to 14,416 applications in 2011.

Table 3: Asylum applications by country of citizenship, 2011-2016

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	Total	In %
Afghanistan	3,609	4,005	2,589	5,076	25,563	11,794	52,636	25.3
Syria	422	915	1,991	7,730	24,547	8,773	44,378	21.3
Iraq	484	491	468	1,105	13,633	2,862	19,043	9.1
Other	9,901	12,002	12,455	14,153	24,597	18,856	91,964	44.2
Total	14,416	17,413	17,503	28,064	88,340	42,285	208,021	100.0

Source: Statistics Austria based on Asylum Statistics by the BM.I.

From a comparative perspective across the EU, Austria ranked second regarding the share of asylum applications in the total population in 2016. Germany ranked first, and Greece and Malta only displayed slightly lower shares than Austria. In absolute numbers, there were 1,259,995 asylum applications in the EU in 2016, a little less than in 2015 (1,322,825). About 3% of those were filed in Austria (source: EUROSTAT database).

In sociodemographic terms, the share of young persons among the refugees is rather high. Among the 208,021 asylum applicants who came between 2011 and 2016, 8.6% (17,847 persons) were unaccompanied minors between the ages of 14 and 18. Around 8% of the unaccompanied minors were younger than 14 (1,442 persons). Regarding gender, there is a clear, albeit slightly vanishing dominance of males. While 26% of the asylum applicants in 2011 were women, this share grew to 33% in 2016. There are many reasons for why these shares are still relatively low. According to the UNHCR, the risks for women who flee is often assessed as being too high in the countries of origin. Married men, therefore, are to some extent the pioneers on the dangerous journey to Europe and try to get their families to join them once they are recognized as refugees. Furthermore, women often lack the financial resources to flee to Europe on their own.

Table 4: Final decisions on asylum, 2011-2016

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	Total
Positive	3,572	3,680	4,133	8,734	14,413	22,307	56,839
Negative	11,553	10,745	10,379	9,068	13,152	13,124	68,021
Other (1)	2,100	1,878	2,163	1,032	8,009	11,313	26,495
Total	17,225	16,303	16,675	18,834	35,574	46,744	151,355
Positive %	20.7	22.6	24.8	46.4	40.5	47.7	37.6
Positive from:							
Afghani- stan	822	969	1,259	2,540	2,083	1,756	9,429
Iraq	202	161	121	211	637	1,328	2,660
Syria	360	542	838	3,604	8,114	15,528	28,986

Note (1): the category 'Other' includes, for example, non-appearance of asylum applicants, return and withdrawal of the application. Source: Statistics Austria based on Asylum Statistics by the BM.I.

Since 2013, the number of final decisions on asylum has been growing according to the number of applications with a peak in 2016 reflecting the logical time lag between the arrival of refugees and the decisions made on their future in Austria. The share of positive decisions (for asylum including subsidiary and humanitarian protection) has also grown significantly from 20.7% in 2011 to 47.7% in 2016. Furthermore, there is a pronounced shift from asylum to the more temporary forms of subsidiary and humanitarian protection. Asylum applicants from Syria have by far the highest chances to be recognized as refugees.

There is also a visible growth trend for the time period under consideration regarding the forced and voluntary return of asylum applicants. According to the BM.I and the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA), 10,677 asylum applicants left Austria in the year 2016, 5,797 left voluntarily and 4,880 were forced to leave the country. The number of returns is significantly higher than it was in 2011, when 4,377 persons were forced to leave or did so on a voluntary basis (3,382).

1.3 Regional distribution of migrants

As shown above, almost one fifth of the Austrian population was born abroad. Regarding their spatial distribution, one can clearly argue that migration to Austria is first and foremost an urban (Viennese) phenomenon. Vienna – the only large metropolis in Austria, its capital as well as its economic, cultural and political center – attracts people from other Austrian provinces and from abroad. The city is home to 40 per cent of the foreign-born population in Austria, compared to only 17 per cent of the Austrian-born population. For migrants from Syria and Iraq, the share of those living in Vienna is even higher (see Table 5).

Table 5: Regional distribution of persons born abroad, 2017

	Austria	Vienna	Vienna in %
Total population	8,772,865	1,867,582	21.3
Born in Austria	7,116,599	1,207,833	17.0
Foreign-born	1,656,266	659,749	39.8
Born in			
Afghanistan	44,684	15,880	35.5
Syria	41,588	18,597	44.7
Iraq	16,147	6,521	40.4

Source: Statistics Austria, Population Register; own calculation.

Map 1 shows pronounced regional disparities in the share of migrants in the total population on the level of political districts. While on the national level the share of foreign-born persons is 18.9%, Vienna takes the lead with a share of 35.3%, followed by other – albeit much smaller – cities like Salzburg (30.4%), Wels (29.7%) and Innsbruck (29.6%). On the other end of the scale, we find very low shares in more rural political districts, mostly in the provinces of Lower Austria and Styria, like Zwettl (3.1%) or Waidhofen an der Thaya (4.4%). The reasons for this distribution are obvious and can be briefly explained as follows: Migrants are most of all attracted to job opportunities in urban labour markets or to education opportunities at universities. They also have better chances through migrant networks in urban areas, a factor which perpetuates migration to cities.

Map 1: Share of foreign-born persons in the total population on the level of political districts, 2017

Source: Population Register, Statistics Austria; cartography: ArcMap 10.3; own design.

Map 2: Regional distribution of migrants born in Syria, Afghanistan and Iraq on the level of political districts, 2017

Source: Population Register, Statistics Austria; cartography: ArcMap 10.3; own design.

At the beginning of 2017, the number of persons born in Syria, Afghanistan and Iraq and residing in Austria was a little more than 100,000 persons, most of whom had arrived around the year 2015 as asylum applicants. Almost 40% of them are currently living in Vienna, while the respective shares in all other political districts never exceed 4% (see Map 2). Once again, capitals of other provinces (like Innsbruck, Salzburg, Linz or Graz) play a certain role but Vienna is still the hotspot for refugees. One has to keep in mind that asylum applicants are only allowed to register for a place of residence within the province that provides them with welfare support. They cannot choose where they want to live, contrary to recognized refugees.

2 The socio-economic, political and cultural context

Austria is located in the south-eastern central part of Europe and shares a border with Slovenia and Italy in the South, Switzerland, Liechtenstein and Germany in the west, the Czech Republic in the north and Slovakia and Hungary in the east. During the Cold War period, Austria was located at the periphery of Western Europe with the Iron Curtain forming its eastern border. In the past 30 years, Central and Eastern Europe have undergone enormous political changes that also went hand in hand with a gradual removal of migration-related barriers. Starting with the fall of the Iron Curtain in 1989, the region witnessed Austria's EU accession in 1995 and the accession of ten mostly Eastern European countries in 2004 as well as the accession of Romania and Bulgaria in 2007.

Austria consists of nine federal provinces including Vienna, the capital. Vienna thus holds a double function within the Austrian constitutional and administrative framework as a city with its own statute and as a federal province. Furthermore, Vienna is the only large metropolis in Austria with 1.87 million inhabitants, accounting for more than one fifth of the Austrian population. Ranking second is the capital of the federal province of Styria, Graz, with 284,000 inhabitants, and ranking third is Linz, the capital of Upper Austria, with a little more than 200,000 inhabitants.

In comparison to other European countries, Austria is rather small both in terms of area and population. In demographic terms, Austria currently is home to 8.74 million persons and has been experiencing a population growth since the turn of the millennium (2001: 8.03 million persons, 2011: 8.37 million persons). This growth is entirely caused by immigration. Furthermore, the demographic composition of the population has changed drastically in the past decades. A rise in life expectancy combined with dropping fertility rates have led to the ongoing ageing of the population. In the past 40 years, the average mean age has grown by about 6 years to 42.2 years (source: Statistics Austria database).

Results from the Human Development Report (UNDP, 2017: 2) indicate that Austria displays a 'very high human development category' (with a score of 0.893), ranking it at 24th place out of 188 countries. The Austrian HDI (Human Development Index) is above average for all countries in the 'very high development group' and also above the average of OECD countries (ibid.: 4). Made up of basically three dimensions (a long and healthy life, access to knowledge and a decent standard of living), the UNDP report shows that Austria's life expectancy at birth grew by 6.1 years between 1990 and 2015, mean years of schooling increased by 2.7 years and the GNI (Gross National Income) per capita increased by about 40%.

According to Statistics Austria (based on the Labour Force Survey), unemployment rates are currently dropping. In 2017, the workforce consisted of 4.261 million employed persons and 247,900 unemployed persons. This results in an unemployment rate of 5.5% in 2017, compared to 6.0% the previous year. In the same time period, the number of gainfully employed persons grew by 49,700 persons. From the gender perspective, dropping unemployment rates refer to both men and women (-0.6% for both genders in comparison to 2016).

Regarding the structure of the population in terms of religion, the only available official data source is the Census 2001, which contained a question about the individual religious denomination. Back then, 74% of the Austrian population were Roman Catholic, 5% Protestant, 4% Muslim and 12% of the population stated that they did not belong to any religious denomination. According to a study that took the data of the Census 2001 as a basis for

projections (Goujon, Jurasszovich and Potancoková, 2017), this distribution has changed in the past 15 years. The group that has grown the most is the one with no religious denomination from 12% to 17%. The share of Roman Catholics has shrunk from 74% to 64%, while the share of Muslims has doubled from 4% to 8%.

The official language in Austria is German. Nevertheless, there are several languages that are officially recognized as minority languages next to German on the municipal level, namely Hungarian and Burgenland Croatian (in some municipalities in Austria's most eastern federal province Burgenland) and Slovenian (in some municipalities of Carinthia). These regulations are based on the protection of minority rights and go back to the Austrian State Treaty of 1955. Most languages spoken by more recent immigrants and pertinent to much larger groups like Turkish are not subject to the protection of minority rights.

Since 1945, Austria has been a federal, representative democratic republic. Its federal character derives from a division of legislative, executive and judicial powers between the federal level, called *Bund*, and the nine provinces that are called *Länder*. Since Austria's accession to the EU in 1995, certain competences have been delegated to the supranational level. The system of government is characterized by a mix of presidential and parliamentary elements, whereby the former is rather weakly pronounced, which leads to it being classified as semi-presidentialism. The parliament has two chambers, the National Council with 183 seats and the Federal Council that assembles delegates from the provinces. The formation of the federal government has historically been rather atypical for a parliamentary system, as Austria displays a longstanding tradition of grand coalitions between the social democrats (Sozialdemokratische Partei Österreichs – SPÖ) and the conservatives (Österreichische Volkspartei – ÖVP) (Pelinka & Rosenberger, 2007). A reason for this is the political culture characteristic of consociational democracies. In the case of Austria, the broad involvement of (non-winning) political minorities strongly evolved around the conflictual experiences of the First Republic (1918-1934) and the aim of conciliation of the class cleavage between capital and labour. It is also in this context that Austrian Corporatism emerged with a continuously high degree of coordination between business and labour stakeholders as well as institutionalized bargaining practices (Pernicka & Helfer, 2015).

Since December 2017, the government consists of a coalition between the conservative ÖVP and the right-wing Freedom Party of Austria (FPÖ). This political constellation is quite the exception and supports arguments for an erosion of consociational democratic patterns that were initially raised during the first ÖVP-FPÖ coalition in 2000. With the fading of the class cleavage, new political issues have moved to the top of the political agenda, most notably matters of immigration and internal security. This has been accompanied by a political culture of conflict and a retreat from grand coalitions. Surveys relating to the latest national elections (SORA/ISA, 2017) suggest a very high political salience of the topics of immigration and asylum and their positive effect on parties on the conservative to right-wing political spectrum. Political parties currently represented in the National Council are the conservative Austrian People's Party (ÖVP) with 62 seats, the Social Democratic Party of Austria (SPÖ) with 52 seats, the right-wing Freedom Party of Austria (FPÖ) with 51 seats, the liberal New Austria and Liberal Forum (NEOS) with 10 seats, and the left-wing List Peter Pilz (PILZ) with 8 seats.

3 The constitutional organization of the state and constitutional principles on immigration and asylum

3.1 The constitutional framework and the principle of asylum

The legal system of Austria has five fundamental principles enshrined in its constitutional framework⁴: the democratic, republican, federal, constitutional and liberal principle. The first three principles are explicitly stated within respective articles of the Austrian Federal Constitutional Law, whereas the latter two are the results of interpretation of the entirety of constitutional laws. While constitutional laws can be amended by a two-third majority in the National Council of the parliament, the abolishment or modification of laws reflecting the fundamental principles requires an additional national referendum. They are largely considered to be placed even above EU law in the Austrian legal hierarchy.

Figure 2: The hierarchical structure of legal order in Austria

Source: own design.

According to these principles, Austria is a parliamentary democracy (democratic principle) where the political will of the people is mainly formulated through representation and the rare use of instruments of direct democracy. The national government is tied to majorities in the parliament that are decisive for the president's decision of appointing a chancellor after national elections.

In accordance to the constitutional principle, the Republic is founded on a clear separation of powers. This means that legislative, executive and judicial powers provide the means for a general rule of law and equality before the law. The equality clause stated in the Basic Law of the State allows for objectively justifiable unequal treatment between unequal persons, meaning between citizens and non-citizens. However, the liberal principle constrains political will in the legislative branch at the level of fundamental and human rights. Those rights were first established under the Geneva Convention, which has been in effect since 1955, as well as under the protocols relating to the status of refugees that came into force in 1973. The second legal source of human rights is the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) provided

⁴ The Austrian constitution does not consist of a single constitutional charter, but of a range of constitutional laws. Two of the historically most central laws are the Federal Constitutional Law (B-VG) that was re-adopted in 1945 in its version of 1929, and the Basic Law of the State on the General Rights of Citizens of 1867 that was ranked as a constitutional law by means of Art. 149, Section 1, B-VG. There is a series of other laws that were adopted as constitutional laws through two-third majority in the National Council.

by the Council of Europe since 1958. Since 1964, the ECHR is ranked as a '[...] directly applicable federal constitutional law in Austria and is therefore formally fully equivalent to the original catalogue of fundamental rights in the Austrian Federal Constitution, the Basic Law of the State on the General Rights of Citizens taken from the 1867 monarchical constitution' (Öhlinger, 1990: 286). Accordingly, although the right to asylum is not explicitly stated in the centrepiece of the Austrian constitutional framework, namely the Federal Constitutional Law, the ECHR as its legal source is in fact ranked as a constitutional law. A third source of fundamental rights is the Charter of Fundamental Human Rights of the European Union. Since it became applicable in 2009, it has not only been coequal to EU primary law but has also been ruled by the Austrian Constitutional Court in 2012 as part of the criteria norms for assessing the constitutional conformity of Austrian law (VfGH-Pressinformation, 2012a).

Finally, in the realm of politics, it is particularly the president who upholds norms and values enshrined in the constitution. He is directly elected as the head of state (republican principle) with extensive competences but also with a tradition of restraint in every-day politics. Also, while he (or she) does generally not have any competences explicitly relating to asylum or immigration, the president is a high moral figure representing the state and can become especially relevant for topics related to human rights.

3.2 Decentralization: Tiers of government and their competences

In accordance with the federal principle, legislative, executive and judicial powers are shared between the federal level and the provincial level. The Austrian provinces (*Länder*) of Burgenland, Carinthia, Lower Austria, Salzburg, Styria, Tyrol, Upper Austria, Vienna, and Vorarlberg participate in the legislative branch in two ways: On the one hand they represent the second and rather weak chamber of the parliament, namely the Federal Council; on the other hand they act in terms of a provincial government that is formed through provincial parliamentary elections. A third tier of government consists of the municipalities, which are called *Gemeinden*. The characterization of Austria as a federal state with a high level of centralization becomes particularly evident when considering the division of competences in the realms of immigration and asylum (see Table 6).

Table 6: Division of important competences in sectors relevant to immigration and asylum

	Federation	Provinces	Municipalities
Legal status Entrance Residence Return	Status of foreigners (L/EX) ⁽¹⁾		
	Control of entry, residence and withdrawal of aliens from national territory (L/EX)	Naturalisation procedure (EX)	-
	Asylum procedure and decision (L/EX)		
	Naturalisation law (L)		
Accommodation Reception	Accommodation as a condition for entrance and residence (L)	Regional planning and building laws (L)	Execution of building laws (EX)
	Accommodation in Initial Reception Centres or Distribution Centres during admissibility procedure in asylum system (L/EX)	Accommodation under Basic Welfare Support during substantive asylum procedure (quota for each province according to number of inhabitants) (EX)	Non-discrimination of foreigners in the provision of humane accommodation (EX)
Social insurance Social aid	Pension, health and unemployment insurance depending on legal status and employment (L/partly EX)	Parts of the health sector (EX), social housing sector, small child care, social aid: Needs-Based Minimum Benefit (L/partly EX)	Execution of provincial legislation via municipality or district authorities (EX)
	Universal services: family support, child care allowances		
Employment	Authorization for employment and as a condition for entrance and stay (L)		-
	Setting of quotas for aliens and execution via Public Employment Service (AMS) (EX)	Only consultative function on quotas for provinces (L)	

Source: Based on Bußjäger, 2007; Sozialministerium, 2016. Note (1): L = Legislation, EX = Execution.

Whereas the federal level is (almost) exclusively responsible for matters of legal status and the related issues of entrance, withdrawal and return, the first two tiers of government share competences in the realm of reception within the asylum system. The federal level is only responsible for accommodation and social aid during the admissibility procedure. The provinces, on the other hand, provide Basic Welfare Support⁵ for official asylum applicants during the substantive procedure (see Chapter 5). They are also responsible for social aid services such as the Needs-Based Minimum Benefit, a service for persons without reasonable subsistence that becomes relevant upon the acquisition of a title.

The 2,098 municipalities have no formal competences in migration-related areas. However, they hold competences regarding the execution of building and space planning, which

⁵ Basic Welfare Support is a social aid system for aliens in need of help and protection (most notably asylum applicants) which covers accommodation, food and clothing, health insurance, and partly spending money.

allow them to have a de facto impact on the urban distribution of migrants and the accommodation of asylum applicants (Rosenberger & Haselbacher, 2016: 402).

3.3 Judiciary and constitutional case-law on asylum

The Austrian judiciary is commonly divided into the subsystems of public, private and criminal law. While the Supreme Court of Justice (OGH) presents the highest national body in criminal and private proceedings, the Constitutional Court (VfGH) is the final instance of the public and constitutional law (see Figure 3). The Federal Administrative Court (BVwG) is of particular relevance for matters of immigration and asylum and functions as an appellate body in administrative procedures such as those concerning international protection. The BVwG was created in 2012 and has since replaced the Asylum Court and other specialized administrative entities. Revisions can be enacted by the VfGH but also by the Administrative High Court (VwGH) against the decisions of the BVwG in light of contradicting or missing decisions from higher instances or open legal questions.

Aside from its function as an appellate body, the VfGH also has the power to set up judicial reviews on the constitutionality of legislative acts. Historically speaking, its activities in the political realms of immigration and asylum have grown since the early 1990s, when questions of the temporality of residences became relevant, migration matters institutionally switched from the social to the interior ministry and the gates of the asylum system gained importance (Bauböck & Perchinig, 2006: 732p.) In the following decades, the political will of rendering access more restrictive and asylum procedures more efficient (see Chapter 4) has accordingly clashed with human rights provisions embedded in the constitution.

Figure 3: Overview of Austrian judiciary

Source: own design.

Regarding the acceleration of asylum procedures, the VfGH has repeatedly ruled in favour of effective legal remedies and longer appeal periods. As early as 1995, it stated 'that the de facto possibility of return cannot substitute effective legal protection' (translated from German; VfSlg 17.340/2004; cited in Ludwig-Boltzmann-Institut, 2016: 6), after provisions on a general omission of suspensory effects of appeals had been introduced. However, it argued that a shortened suspensory period is constitutional in the case of second-time applicants because in this case the asylum law held provisions for an examination of refoulement protection prior to cutting guarantees.

Similarly, in October 2017, the VfGH found itself for the third time in two years faced with provisions on the appeal period for decisions concerning international protection at first instance that are associated with residence terminating measures. It annulled the federal government's two-week provision and stressed the relevance of legal remedy that stood in contrast to the BVwG, which had arguably been inefficient with its proceedings. Accordingly, the BFA Procedures Act had to be repaired after the VfGH had already invalidated a general two-week appeal provision in 2016 (VfGH-Presseinformation, 2017a).

The most comprehensive legal intervention of the VfGH occurred in 2004, after the first conservative/right-wing coalition government had introduced restrictions for appeal to administrative decisions, immediate expulsion of asylum applicants and increased possibilities for detention (Kotschy, 2006: 689). The VfGH invalidated a major part of the new provisions as they violated a number of fundamental rights such as the right to an effective remedy (new facts and evidence were not allowed in the second instance), physical and mental integrity (immediate enforceability of decisions), liberty (detention upon missing interviews and follow-up applications), family life and property (confiscation of clothing and personal belongings) (Kotschy, 2006). According to Kotschy (2006: 693) the central rationale behind the judgment was balancing the interests of asylum applicants as a vulnerable group of applicants on the one hand and the state and its security concerns on the other.

Since 2011, the VfGH has largely ruled in favour of individual rights. This concerns, for example, family reunification in asylum procedures, where it decided that the notion of family members in terms of the ECHR does not have to be congruent with that of the Settlement and Residence Act. Also, it ruled in 2014 and 2015 that the right to respect for private and family life needs to be considered during the family asylum procedure (Lukits, 2016b: 59).

With regard to procedural guarantees, the VfGH (G 151/2014) annulled increasingly restrictive provisions on appeal during detention due to a lack of clarity as to where legal remedy has to be lodged (VfGH-Presseinformation, 2015). In 2016, it found that a legal differentiation between mere consultative work of legal counsellors during appeals on the one hand and representation during appeals to return decisions or decisions terminating residence on the other hand discriminates between aliens and is objectively unfounded (VfGH 9.3.2016 G447-449/2015). Legal counsellors may thus represent their clients upon demand at any appeal (Kriwanek & Tuma, 2016).

Finally, concerning the entry and withdrawal from territory the VfGH invalidated minimum sanctions (1,000 EUR) for unlawful entry to territory (VfGH 9.3.2011 G 53/2010) as not sufficiently differentiated and also annulled the termination of procedures for settlement permits of persons who had to leave the country as it was violating the constitutional principle (VfGH 20.2.2011 G 201/2010) (VfGH-Presseinformation, 2011). Likewise, in 2012, a provision of the Aliens Police Act that had blocked authorities to reverse entry bans upon the termination of

relevant grounds was declared unconstitutional (VfGH 3.12.2012 G74/2012) (VfGH-
Presseinformation, 2012b).

4 The relevant legislative and institutional framework in the fields of migration and asylum

4.1 State actors

At the highest institutional level, matters of asylum, immigration and integration are subject to the portfolios of three major ministries (see Figure 4.):

- The Federal Ministry of the Interior (BM.I): It covers matters related to federal borders, immigration and emigration, return, citizenship as well as asylum. The BFA works as a subordinated agency that carries out first instance procedures on asylum and issues residence titles as well as return decisions (EMN, 2015: 85).
- The Federal Ministry for Europe, Integration and Foreign Affairs (BMEIA): It is responsible for visa issuance, which is linked to the diplomatic authorities abroad, as well as (development) cooperation with third states and the UNHCR. Since 2014, the BMEIA is officially responsible for the integration agenda. It largely finances the ÖIF (Austrian Integration Fund) as an organization that manages integration projects and regularly produces evaluation papers (EMN, 2015: 85).
- The Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection (BMASK): It determines criteria and quotas for work permits. The AMS as a subordinated administrative body for labour market matters executes the permissions, performs consultative work and provides qualification courses (EMN, 2015: 85).

Figure 4: National institutions involved in immigration and asylum

Source: Figure based on institutional chart by EMN, 2015: 85.

Major institutional rearrangements have been in place since 2011, when a State Secretariat for Integration was created. This brought about a shift of this policy field from the interior ministry to the exterior ministry, where it was fully incorporated in 2014. Like immigration and asylum matters as a whole, this matter remained in the hands of the ÖVP, which for almost two decades has dominated the interior and the exterior ministry, whereas the SPÖ was en-

trusted with social affairs. This has changed only recently, when the ÖVP entered into a coalition with the political competitor FPÖ, which had a strong political ownership of these topics during its time in the opposition and during elections. Since December 2017, an independent candidate recruited by the FPÖ constitutes the exterior minister, while two long-serving FPÖ politicians are interior and social ministers.

Apart from political personnel, it is important to, firstly, highlight the Austrian Ombudsman Board as a control authority for public administration including an expert commission on the protection and promotion of human rights (Volksanwaltschaft, 2017). Secondly, academic expertise was institutionalized in recent years with the creation of the Independent Expert Council for Integration in 2010 within the BMEIA and the Migration Council for Austria created within the BM.I in 2014. These two councils were recruited by the respective institutional authorities and are assigned to produce annual reports evaluating the status quo and giving advice for future actions.

Furthermore, in 2015, the Austrian government installed two Refugee Coordinators as part of an ad hoc crisis management. An immediate jump in the number of people seeking asylum or travelling through Austria exceeded the reception capacities and urged authorities to create these posts (Profil, 2016). Up until late 2016, they were responsible for organizing accommodation for refugees through a coordination network of diverse actors such as federal, provincial and municipal authorities, economic actors and NGOs. Especially the latter play a crucial role within the fields of asylum and immigration, which is why we will briefly zoom in on their activities in the Austrian asylum system.

4.2 Non-governmental and civil society actors

NGOs are engaged both as legally associated partners of state authorities but also as independent actors who work in favour of refugees' and immigrants' rights beyond legal provisions. Historically speaking, they have emerged from a Christian social environment (for example: Caritas, Diakonie) on the one hand and social democratic organizations as well as new social movements on the other (for example: Volkshilfe, Asyl in Not, SOS Menschenrechte) (Langthaler & Trauner, 2009: 456). Their engagement has not only been tied to institutional needs since the 1990s, but is also linked to the rise of broad civil society concerns, which peaked in 1999 with the deportation death case of Marcus Omofuma, the Refugee Protest Camp Vienna in 2012 as well as diverse initiatives during the summer of 2015.

Today, NGOs engage in numerous fields of activity such as consultative work within asylum procedures, the provision of certain basic welfare services for applicants as well as integration and voluntary return programmes (Langthaler & Trauner, 2009: 452).

Regarding the recruitment of legal advisory staff for applicants to international protection, two NGOs are of particular relevance as they are assigned by the federal government for counselling: Verein Menschenrechte Österreich (VMÖ) and Diakonie Flüchtlingsdienst (together with Volkshilfe Oberösterreich).

Concerning care services, NGOs have experienced a profound institutional involvement in the provision of accommodation and social workers. This has particularly been performed by certain divisions of Caritas and Diakonie-Flüchtlingsdienst. In this context, NGOs act as 'operative partners of the provinces for the performance of care tasks' (Langthaler & Trauner,

2009: 460). They cooperate by means of service contracts with the provinces and are accordingly tied to legal provisions regarding the scope of activities covered by public finance. Public financing is generally provided for the accommodation of asylum applicants, whereas for counselling tasks, care services and integration programmes they receive funding from the European Refugee Fund and are only co-financed by the interior ministry (Langthaler & Trauner, 2009: 457).

However, in some areas Langthaler and Trauner (2009: 464) have noted a loss of importance of charitable NGOs to the benefit of private social service contractors such as European Home Care and VMÖ. Recent announcements of the federal government, on the other hand, have expressed the wish to push back NGOs in order to benefit centralized state agencies (Profil, 2018).

4.3 National immigration and asylum law: pillars, principles and evolution

The first pillar of Austrian immigration and asylum law encompasses the realm of regular migration. The Settlement and Residence Act (NAG) (100/2005) as a general national law governs legal residence permits and accordingly provides for an active management of certain types of immigration. Aside from the documentation of EU internal mobility, the NAG formulates the conditions of permission, rejection and withdrawal of residence titles, arguably matters of a stay longer than six months. Whereas the term ‘residence’ refers to the aim of finding a residency for more than six months, relocating the centre of life interests or taking on a long-term job, ‘settlement’ addresses a form of immigration that can solidify and allows for family reunification (Feik, 2016: 173). This distinction is characteristic of Austrian immigration law (EMN, 2015).

The second pillar governs the entrance to federal territory, the grounds for rejection as well as the issuance of residence terminating measures, return, toleration and the issuance of documents for foreigners (Feik, 2016: 156). The most important laws are the Aliens Police Act (FPG) (100/2005) and the Border Control Act (GrekoG) (435/1996), which is informed by the Schengen provisions.

The third pillar covers the realm of asylum. Next to national law, this area consists of a complex layering of primary law in terms of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, EU secondary law as well as further national law. The Asylum Act (AsylG) (100/2005) governs obligations stipulated in the Geneva Convention and under European Union law. It holds provisions for asylum applicants and beneficiaries of international protection with regard to entry, identification and qualification while the BFA Proceeding-Act (BFA-VG) covers procedural aspects (Rössl & Frühwirth, 2016).

Immigration- and asylum-related legislation has experienced a particular boost in quantity since the early 1990s. This also led to a constant transformation in the structure of laws. For example, the Aliens Act was created in 1992 as a follow-up to the former Aliens Police Act and merged together with the Residence Act in 1997 – only to be separated again into the Foreign Police Act (FPG) and Settlement and Residence Act (NAG), which form the legal basis of current provisions since 2005. In addition to that, laws often entail only formal structures and procedures, whereas national regulations from the respective ministries provide details for the implementation (EMN, 2015: 21).

During the 1990s and early 2000s, the paradigm of Austrian asylum and immigration policies was restricting access through the asylum system while disengaging from a proactive migration management after decades of ‘guest worker’ politics (Bauböck & Perchinig, 2006). Regarding asylum, the goal was to increase efficiency, such as with safe third country provisions and the abolishment of in-country applications to visas in 1992, the introduction of accelerated asylum procedures for ‘evidently unfounded’ applications in 2005 or a shortening of appeal periods in 2009. On the other hand, liberalizations concern, for example, the solidification of residence with increasing time spent in Austria. This principle is embedded in the Aliens Act of 1997 and aimed at integrating the prevalent foreign population (Bauböck & Perchinig, 2006: 734). Also, following a ruling of the VfGH (G 246, 247/07), an instrument for the regularization of persons with an irregular or precarious status was created in 2009⁶. The humanitarian right to stay allows persons that can de facto not be returned to apply for a residence permit (Chapter 5) (Demokratiezentrum-Wien, 2015). Regarding labour migration, the introduction of seasonal work permits through the Aliens Act (FrG) (75/1997) was the only major innovation next to general restrictions to the mere immigration of key labour forces such as academics.

2011 marked a turning point in national labour migration management. Following the EU directive 2009/50/EC, Austria transposed provisions on the immigration of highly qualified labour through a new quota system and criteria catalogue for the so-called ‘Red-White-Red Card’. This provision was further extended in 2013 by the possibility to apply for the card abroad under a point-based criteria system.

Regarding the realm of asylum and its procedural dimension, Austrian lawmakers particularly increased security concerns over the internal dealing with asylum applicants since 2011. While the 2009 reform contained obligations for applicants to international protection to reside within the district of their Initial Reception Centres during the admissibility procedure (Rössel & Frühwirth, 2016), according provisions were extended to persons with return decisions. The 2017 Aliens Law Amendment Act (145/2017) further expanded this logic to asylum applicants in the substantive procedure who are currently obliged to reside within the province of their Basic Welfare Support system (Knapp, 2017). This was mainly implemented in order to avoid secondary movements from rural to urban areas and from one social aid system to another. Since 2017, persons in the admissibility procedure can furthermore be ordered to remain not only within their municipality but within a given accommodation facility. This applies, for example, to persons arriving from safe third countries and to second-time applicants (Biffel, 2017: 7).

Following the 2015 Aliens Law Amendment Act (70/2015), the admissibility procedure was locally shifted from the initial reception centre to the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA) and fast track procedures with a maximum decision period of 5 months were legally anchored for certain groups of applicants (Rössel & Frühwirth, 2016). The same aliens law

⁶ Prior to the amendment act of 2009, the granting of a residence title on humanitarian grounds only existed in terms of a non-binding right based on clemency. In 2008, the VfGH (G 246, 247/07) found that old provisions were illicit. Persons whose residence could not be terminated due to Art. 8 ECHR had been living as illegalized immigrants in a legal black hole. Consequently the federal government was urged to create residence permits that could be claimed on humanitarian grounds, namely if a person displays strong private and family ties within the federal territory.

amendment contained provisions for the creation of annual country reports (for the top 5 countries of origin by holders of international protection), which form the basis for reviewing asylum cases.

Liberalizations in this area were introduced, for example, following the EU directive on return 2008/115/EC, when free legal consultation was extended in asylum and return proceedings in 2011 as well as with the expansion of legal advice before the VwGH in 2015 (EMN, 2015: 23pp). In 2013, a new institutional structure of asylum was created. The establishment of the BFA and the incorporation of the Asylum Court into the newly founded BVwG re-opened the legal channels to the VwGH (Rössel & Frühwirth, 2016).

With regard to the material dimension of asylum, the most important change occurred with the 2016 Amendment Act (24/2016) modifying the AsylG, the FPG and BFA-VG as a direct legislative response to the perceived crisis. The protection and thus residence period for beneficiaries of asylum was limited to three years, downgrading the status to the minimum limit stipulated in the EU Qualification Directive 2011/95/EU. In addition, time limits were introduced for family reunification, within which beneficiaries of subsidiary protection can bring their family members into the country after three years and recognized refugees within the first three months upon acquiring a title (ÖIF, 2016). Eventually, legal provisions were created that allow for a governing via an emergency decree, when the annual upper limit of asylum applicants is exhausted (Hilpold, 2017)⁷. It allows authorities to suspend the processing of further applications. However, this mechanism has not entered into force as of early 2018.

By 2017, political discourse on immigration and asylum in Austria was tightly associated with matters of internal security and identity (Rheindorf & Wodak, 2017). This is mirrored by the legal reform package on integration and anti-face-covering (IntG, AGesVG, IJG), which stipulates compulsory civic integration programs for beneficiaries of international protection as well as a ban of face veiling clothes in public. The Aliens Law Amendment Act 2017, furthermore, tightened provisions on detention (as had already been done in 2011 and 2015) with detention periods for adults of up to 18 months.

4.4 Sub-national legislation in conflict with national legislation

In recent years, the reception and accommodation of asylum applicants within the federal Austrian territory has been a central site of political contestation. The conflict between federal and provincial actors peaked in 2015, when application numbers rose sharply. Following the

⁷ The 2016 Amendment Act (24/2016) introduced changes to the AsylG (Section 5 §36 and §41), thereby attaching the admission of newly arriving persons into the asylum procedure to the warranty of public order. The evaluation of the public order is conducted with regard to the number of foreigners applying for international protection, and the public systems that might be curtailed in their functioning. Therefore, the federal government publishes a yearly annual upper limit figure (37,500 applicants in 2016). Upon the exhaustion of this limit, the federal government after consultation of the main committee of the National Council may govern via an ordinance for up to 18 months. This mechanism has not been activated as of April 2018, given the fact that application figures remained under the stipulated limits. However, the provision has been subject to heavy criticism of legal experts who doubt the legitimacy of a security based argument against obligations deriving from the Geneva Convention (Hilpold, 2017: 76-77). Representatives of the federal government have pointed out a possible implementation via the installation of waiting zones (ORF, 2016).

2004 agreement on Basic Welfare Support, provinces are required to take on asylum applicants according to a quota (in relation to the size of population). However, some provinces and municipalities were not willing to provide accommodation facilities or encountered public resistance. Following disputes with the federal government, the latter adopted a constitutional law, namely the Federal Constitutional Act for the Accommodation and Distribution of Foreigners in Need of Help and Protection (120/2015). It allows the federal government to run its own accommodation facilities in federal public buildings, even against the will of provincial and municipal authorities (Müller & Rosenberger, 2017: 119p.).

The matter of a social aid service, namely the Needs-Based Minimum Benefit as a provincial competence, has also been subject to several political and jurisdictional conflicts between the federal or constitutional level and the respective provinces. Between 2010 and 2016, an agreement of the federal government and the provinces on common standards in central areas of social aid provided a stronger harmonization regarding minimum allowances and personal asset limits, to name a few. However, since the beginning of 2017, the provinces are able to freely act upon their own legislation, as previous negotiations on a new agreement failed. Political tensions emerged particularly between the SPÖ-led social ministry on the federal level and ÖVP-led provinces that aimed for more restrictive provisions (Salzburger Nachrichten, 2016). The most restrictive provisions were introduced in Upper Austria, Lower Austria and in Burgenland, where allowances were cut and upper household limits and the provision of aid were determined by the duration of residence. In Lower Austria, beneficiaries of subsidiary protection were excluded from the full service of Needs-Based Minimum Benefit. Following a complaint of a person based in this province, the VfGH (E 3297/2016) ruled in 2017 that this discrimination is lawful by pointing out the temporary character of the title in comparison to asylum (VfGH-Presseinformation, 2017b). However, in a 2018 ruling, the VfGH (G 136/2017) annulled provisions that stipulated upper household limits and generally attached services to the length of residence (VfGH-Presseinformation, 2018)⁸. Furthermore, the western provinces of Tyrol and Vorarlberg cut allowances and introduced special provisions for persons who share flats. The remaining provinces introduced only moderate changes that mainly tied allowances to the completion of integration courses (Wiener-Zeitung, 2017).

A third site of conflict concerns civic integration programmes and the question of whether asylum applicants should be allowed to engage. Diverging objectives are particularly evident in the case of the province of Vienna. Against the federal point of view (of the BMEIA) that integration measures should generally only be considered for beneficiaries of international protection, Viennese authorities (FSW and MA17) installed an operative system of integration

⁸ With regard to the VfGH ruling E 3287/2016 relating to the case of an Iraqi national, the judges found that differences in the legal status of holders of subsidiary protection and beneficiaries of asylum are in fact sufficient to justify an objective discrimination when it comes to social services. Yet, the judges pointed out the necessity of complying with Art. 3 of the ECHR in assessing the level of services (VfGH-Presseinformation, 2017b). Regarding the VfGH ruling G 136/2017, the decision is argued as follows: 'The system [Deckelung, Anm.] that has been created with § 11b NÖ MSG does not conduct an averaging, but rather prevents considerations of a concrete need of persons living in a household. Therefore the system of Needs-Based Minimum Income fails to fulfil its purpose, namely the prevention and countering of social hardship of persons in need of help' (own translation from German; VfGH 7.3.2018 G 136/2017; cited in: VfGH-Presseinformation, 2018).

courses for persons with an ongoing procedure. These encompass German courses, workshops and information classes on different topics (Start Wien) and cooperation with the Public Employment Service.

4.5 Policy plans and roadmaps

Recent policy plans on the federal level have been put forth in a ‘50-Points-Integration Plan’ that was developed by the BMEIA and the Expert Commission in an immediate response to the summer of 2015. Some of the proposed measures in the realms of education and language, intercultural dialogue, regional living environment and labour skills (BMEIA, 2015) have already found consideration in the aforementioned 2017 legislation.

Another, more recent roadmap on immigration, asylum and integration was laid down in December 2017 in the last government program (2018 – 2022) by the coalition partners of the ÖVP and the FPÖ (Bundeskanzleramt, 2017). In the chapter on ‘order and security’ (pp. 32-33), it defines goals such as a recodification of immigration and asylum law or the promotion of ideas during the Austrian EU Council Presidency in the second half of 2018. Central issues are the protection of EU external borders described as a condition for returning to Schengen provisions, making asylum procedures more efficient by screening communication devices in order to investigate travel routes and cutting legal remedies before the VwGH in certain cases. Under ‘social matters’ (p. 118) the program stipulates a reduction of financial transfers for persons granted asylum or subsidiary protection to a monthly 365 EUR plus a 155 EUR integration bonus upon the engagement in integration courses (but also sanctions upon disregard), despite this being a provincial competence.

Finally, the program refers to the ‘migration crisis of 2015’ and argues for the creation of a legal framework that allows for specific arrangement competences and information obligations between tiers of government in the context of future crisis management (Bundeskanzleramt, 2017: 35).

5 The legal status of foreigners

5.1 Regular migration

Legal entrance into the federal territory of Austria generally requires a valid passport and visa. Groups that are exempted from visa obligations are stipulated in the Foreign Police Act (FPG) (100/2005) and encompass EEA citizens, third country nationals with a settlement in the Schengen Area, citizens of third countries holding bilateral agreements with Austria and beneficiaries of international protection (EMN, 2015: 29).

The first two types of visa are governed by the EU Visa Code Regulation (2009/810/EC) and the Schengen Borders Code (2006/562/EC). Visa A grants holders airport transit and Visa C permits for short stays of up to three months. The third type, Visa D, is a national long-stay visa allowing for a stay of up to six months. As laid down in the FPG, it can be issued for the purpose of a stay beyond three months, in exceptional humanitarian cases, for job-seeking, the attribution of residence permits or the purpose of family reunification under asylum law. Unless attached to the asylum system, applying for Visa D requires health insurance that covers at least 30,000 EUR, proof of financial resources and in case of no application for residence in Austria proof of employment and residence in the country of origin (EMN, 2015: 29p). Since the 2017 Aliens Law Amendment Act (145/2017), special provisions are in place allowing for a stay of up to 12 months with Visa D, primarily in cases of attending courses in Austria or for bridging periods until a residence permit is granted which was applied for prior to entry (§ 2 Section 2 NAG 2005). Seasonal workers may also receive a Visa D for a period of nine months and even extend it from within Austria in particular cases.

Applications to any kind of residence permit generally need to be lodged outside of Austria at a responsible embassy or consulate, only renewals of already received titles can be conducted in Austria. Likewise, the approval of an application does not allow for immediate entry, but first requires a granting of a Visa D.

Types of residence permits

Aliens who want to reside or settle in Austria beyond periods and matters provided under the aforementioned visa system need to apply for a residence permit. Different types of permits are issued for different purposes, whereby a general distinction is made between applicants who intend to relocate their centre of main life interests and aim at permanently settling in Austria and those who want to temporarily reside in the country for a specific occupation (category 'Temporary Residence Permit' in Table 7) (EMN, 2015: 32).

Table 7: Residence titles of third country nationals in Austria

Residence permit type	Entitlements
Red-White-Red Card	temporary settlement with restricted access to the labour market, for one year
Red-White-Red Card Plus	temporary settlement with unrestricted access to the labour market, for three years
EU Blue Card	temporary settlement with restricted access to the labour market, for two years
Settlement Permit	temporary settlement with restricted access to the labour market, for a maximum of three years
Settlement Permit without Employment	temporary settlement without employment possibilities, for a maximum of three years
Settlement Permit Dependant	temporary settlement without access to the labour market, for a maximum of three years
Permanent Residence EU	permanent settlement with unrestricted access to the labour market, for five years
Family Member ⁹	family members of Austrian nationals, for a maximum of three years, with the possibility of subsequently obtaining the residence title Permanent Residence EU
Temporary Residence Permit	temporary residence for a specific purpose; several subcategories, issued for one year, this includes the Residence Permit Plus and Residence Permit for Individual Protection, which can be issued based on humanitarian grounds

Source: own compilation, based on EMN (2015, p.32, Table 4).

Conditions for granting a residence permit

General conditions for any type of residence title are stipulated under §11-13 of the Settlement and Residence Act (NAG) (100/2005) and encompass the necessity to find adequate accommodation in advance, have health insurance that covers all major risks and provide evidence for sufficient financial resources (in order to be independent from social aid services), to name a few. Persons aiming at long-term settlement also have to show proof of German language skills at the level of A1. General grounds for refusal are entry bans, return decisions within an EEA member state as well as convictions on previous illegal entry (EMN, 2015: 35).

Austrian legislators have also been pursuing the establishment of a quota system since the early 1990s as an additional condition for entry. While quotas were abolished for highly qualified third country nationals in 2011, the federal government continues to set up annual

⁹ Family members in terms of the NAG are defined as marital partners who are at least 21 years old and their underage children. The definition of family according to the AsylG does not require a certain age, but merely that the partners were married prior to entry.

quotas for certain types of family reunification, holders of a Settlement Permit Dependant applying for a Red-White-Red Card Plus and mid-to-low qualified persons who apply for a Permanent Residence EU in order to pursue employment (EMN, 2015: 35). The federal quota for 2018 encompasses 6,120 open slots, 4,000 of which are reserved for seasonal workers (Kurier.at, 2018).

The NAG stipulates legal remedies against negative decisions on applications or the renewal of applications before the High Administrative Court (EMN, 2015: 40).

Rights and duties upon granting a status

Persons who are granted a residence or settlement title can legally reside within the entire federal territory for the time of validity of their status. A renewal can be undertaken at internal authorities at the earliest three months prior to expiry. Immigrants with a long-term stay are required to fulfil the so-called Integration Agreement within their first two years in Austria. Stipulated in the NAG, the agreement obliges immigrants to participate in language and civic integration courses upon the acquisition of a residence permit. The first module encompasses language courses at the level of A2, while the second module covers the level of B1.

Third country nationals are generally entitled to family reunification within the scope of the nuclear family, which is defined in terms of spouses, registered partners and unmarried underage children. The status of those family members is tied to the holder of the Austrian legal status and its validity (EMN, 2015: 36).

In general, access to the labour market is strongly regulated in Austria. Accordingly, the Federal Act Governing the Employment of Foreigners (AuslBG) (218/1975) differentiates between types of residence that entail automatic access, conditioned access and a third category of persons who are fully excluded from the labour market. The first group are for example holders of the Red-White-Red Card Plus, the Permanent Residence-EU, or Residence Permit Plus. Persons with a conditioned access need to apply for a work permit at the Austrian Public Employment Service (AMS). Those can be persons aiming to conduct seasonal work, students, holders of a toleration card, or asylum applicants three months after admission to the asylum procedure. This group undergoes a labour market test, wherein their immigration situation and the labour market needs are tested, permitting only for work if no Austrian nationals are available and only in sectors of labour shortage (EMN, 2015: 43).

5.2 Immigration via the asylum system

Upon the arrival of persons who want to seek asylum within the Austrian territory, an application needs to be lodged at any police authority. As a member of the Schengen Area with no external borders, Austria generally only has border posts installed at international airports. However, since September 2015 systematic border controls are being conducted along certain frontier checkpoints in accordance with Schengen exemption clauses. The first police authorities that are addressed upon arrival are responsible for immediate registration (which includes taking fingerprints) while third country nationals are generally de facto protected from forced return (EMN, 2015: 45). After a first inquiry with an interpreter is recorded within a maximum of 48 hours in police custody, the documents including a report of the inquiry are submitted to the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA). It is important to note that

only the following prognosis decision about the likeliness of Austrian responsibility for the respective case marks the formal starting point of any asylum procedure (HELPGv, 2018a; BFA, 2018a). Consequently, persons are transferred to a Distribution Centre or invited to present themselves at one of the two Initial Reception Centres.

Reception conditions during the admissibility procedure

The first phase of the twofold asylum procedure is the admissibility procedure during which the BFA checks whether Austria is responsible for an asylum case. During the period of this pending decision (20 days), applying persons carry a green identification card and are obliged to cooperate at any time. They have no legal residence as such and are merely tolerated within the territory of their Distribution or Reception Centre's district. The violation of these borders is considered an administrative offence that can lead to detention in the most extreme case (Rössl & Frühwirth, 2016). During their stay at the reception centre, the persons receive a medical examination, are provided legal support by an NGO and are protected from a forced return. This protection generally is not effective for subsequent applications. Those applicants are not considered for a substantive procedure unless the state of evidence regarding a person's persecution has changed.

Unaccompanied minors are accommodated in special facilities or living communities where they receive 24-hour supervision and social care; in case of doubt they need to undergo an age test by means of a wristbone x-ray. During the admissibility procedure they are represented by their legal adviser.

The first interview and the Dublin procedure

The BFA makes its decision based on an interview (with interpreters) about the person's personal circumstances, his/her journey to Austria and the reasons for his/her flight. Since 2017, every false testimony in this interview is considered a legal offence. Applications are only considered admissible if a person was unable to find protection in another safe third country or if no other EU member state is responsible for the examination (EMN, 2015: 46).

If during the admissibility procedure the BFA finds that any of the criteria or provisions of the Dublin III Regulation apply or if biometric data corresponds to that in the EURODAC database, Austrian authorities enter into a consultative procedure with institutions in the respective member state (BFA, 2018b). In this procedure, time limits for return requests become effective: 3 months upon a negative decision of the BFA, 2 months upon a EURODAC hit and reversely 2 months to reply in regular cases. The person applying for international protection, on the other hand, has an appeal period of 7 days. He/She can turn to the Federal Administrative Court (BVwG), which needs to decide within 7 days upon accepting the case. If the person does not cooperate on his/her return to his/her respective member state, Basic Welfare Support is reduced by withdrawing, for example, spending money and schooling and clothing allowances. Once Austrian authorities have received a positive reply from a Dublin state, the authorities have 6 months to conduct the return. The applicant, on the other hand, cannot be granted a suspension despite an ongoing appeal. In case of an accepted appeal, the person can return to Austria with a white card for temporary residence but may not automatically be accepted for a substantive examination, if there was a mere procedural error (Knapp, 2016b: 3).

Since 2015, the lawmaker also provides details on legal cases of accelerated procedures that are referred to as ‘fast track procedures’. In general, these are enforced when a person’s application is ‘evidently unfounded’, meaning the applicant has arrived from or crossed through a safe third country,¹⁰ has tried to hide their identity or does not state reasons of persecution. These cases need to be ruled upon within a maximum of five months, though negative decisions do not have a suspensory effect (EMN, 2015: 25).

Asylum applicants: Reception conditions and the substantive procedure

In case of a positive outcome in the admissibility procedure, a person is formally recognized as an asylum applicant with a corresponding white temporary residence card that is valid during the entire substantive procedure. It grants persons legal residence within the entire federal territory (EMN, 2015: 52). However, applicants are only allowed to register for a place of residence within the province that provides their Basic Welfare Support.

Basic Welfare Support is a social aid system for aliens in need of help and protection which can be provided through cash or in-kind allowances. This means that, aside from asylum applicants, beneficiaries of international protection are also entitled to this service during the first four months upon approval. Furthermore, persons with legally binding residence terminating decisions and persons that can de facto not be returned have a claim to this type of support until their effective departure. Persons who have private earnings or support are generally excluded from this service. Basic Welfare Support represents the central pillar of the asylum reception system and encompasses (according to Koppenberg, 2014: 44-45):

- accommodation which can be provided by NGOs or provincial bodies or through cash support (120 EUR/month) for individual private rent (special facilities are provided for unaccompanied minors and care-dependent persons, who receive 2,480 EUR/month),
- clothing and food (three meals per day in organized accommodations or a maximum of 215 EUR/month for individually accommodated persons),
- health insurance,
- social consultation,
- spending money (40 EUR/month) in the provinces of Vienna, Tyrol, Vorarlberg.
- For children, school attendance is compulsory, regardless of their status.

This list of important basic welfare provisions is based on the legal framework of the 2004 Basic Welfare Support Agreement of the federal government, which finances services that are implemented on the provincial level. The 60 percent of the budget that are generally derived from the federal level amounted to a total of 473 Mio. EUR in 2017 and have been complemented by respective provincial budgets. As of November 2017, 63.356 persons received Basic Welfare Support (DerStandard, 2017).

Apart from means of reception, recent provisions stipulate the possibility for asylum applicants with a ‘high probability of approval’ to participate in modular integration programs. However, the lawmaker does not offer a comprehensive definition for assessing related ‘probabilities’. Such integration programs entail German and value courses provided by the ÖIF as well

¹⁰ The list of safe countries of origin has been expanded in 2018 to include Ukraine, Armenia and Benin. These were added to such states as Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Georgia, Ghana, Mongolia, Albania, Serbia and Kosovo.

as skill checks and training by the AMS for labour market participation. Currently, most civic integration programs for asylum applicants are only conducted in the province of Vienna. While asylum applicants generally do not have access to the labour market, they can engage in supporting activities in their Basic Welfare Support accommodation or charitable public tasks without a work permit. With a permit from the AMS they can also conduct seasonal work or start an apprenticeship in an area of labour shortage if they are under 25 years of age (AMS-OÖ, 2015). Furthermore, since 2017, they are allowed to conduct simple kinds of work in private households (Biffl, 2017: 7). Unaccompanied underage asylum applicants receive additional support. They are usually accommodated within special facilities with fewer people and increased permanent social staff. There is no general provision for asylum applicants concerning family reunification.

While the status of asylum applicants is associated with a series of rights, this group has been increasingly confronted with new duties in recent years. The latest of such obligations presents the duty to register for a place of residence within the province (*Wohnsitzbeschränkung*) that is responsible for their Basic Welfare Support during the entire asylum procedure (Knapp, 2017: 29). While this, of course, does not apply to those who are self-financed, the necessity to seek permission to move to another province has been criticised for its conformity with EU law (Ludwig-Boltzmann-Institut, 2017: 4). ‘Due to reasons of public interest, the public order or for a quick processing of the application’ (translated from German; Knapp, 2017: 28), authorities are also entitled to delegate an asylum applicant to a specific Basic Welfare Support accommodation. This can be the case if a person was delinquent, if he or she comes from a ‘safe third country’ or if it is the second time that the person applies for asylum in Austria.

The second interview

While Austrian law is only familiar with a single category of application for international protection, there are at least three different statuses that might derive from a respective procedure. During the substantive or regular procedure, applicants are interviewed for the second time providing reasons for why they are seeking asylum in Austria. BFA authorities are inclined to examine, whether there is an entitlement to asylum, subsidiary protection or humanitarian protection. There is an ex officio duty for investigating all possible relevant information and pieces of evidence (Limberger, 2017: 173). The co-presence of a legal representative is possible and means of evidence can be submitted. Up until May 2018, the BFA is authorised to a decision period of 15 months, which will then be revised to the initial provision of six months (Knapp, 2017).

With regard to qualification criteria, authorities first examine whether persecution in terms of Art. 1 of the Geneva Convention applies in a case. While political opinions represent the most common reason for persecution, other aspects have been jurisdictionally more contested. Belonging to a religious minority or changing inner convictions (conversion) that cannot be freely exercised might present a well-founded reason, if the chances are high that it leads to persecution. Yet, although it has proven difficult to assess inner convictions, current procedures foresee the questioning of knowledge on the ‘new’ religion (Limberger, 2017: 176). With regard to belonging to a social group, an ECJ ruling of 2013 (C-199/12 to C-201/12) has pointed out, for example, that persons cannot be expected to hide their homosexuality in the country of origin (Limberger, 2017: 177). Another social group might be that of women with a ‘western orientation’. Concerning this aspect, the VwGH has ruled that such a claim might be

justified even after adopting said orientation in the host country (Limberger, 2017: 179). In this sense, subjective post-flight reasons for asylum in general (but also objective ones) are acknowledged. On the other hand, applications where inner state flight alternatives had been an option are rejected (Limberger, 2017: 182).

As long as a person's residence in Austria is based on entrance and reception provisions under the Asylum Act, he/she is not allowed to lodge an application for residence under the NAG (EMN, 2015: 52p.).

A special asylum procedure is foreseen for families. If several family members lodge an application for international protection, their cases are commonly examined, although each family member receives a separate written decision. Granting protection to one family member automatically leads to protection being granted to the remaining family members. However, the legal term of family in this context is very narrow. It only covers the relationship between underage unmarried children and their parents, marital or registered partners as well as legal representatives of underage children (all three statuses need to be acquired prior to arrival) (HELPgv, 2018b).

Likewise, there are again special provisions for unaccompanied minors with regard to the substantive procedure. These persons are legally represented by legal staff of the respective provincial children and youth aid authorities (*Kinder- und Jugendhilfe*). Like all other applicant groups they have an appeal period of four weeks following unfavourable decisions after the substantive procedure.

Beneficiaries of international protection: rights and duties

Upon the granting of asylum, recognized refugees receive a Convention Passport which entitles them to residence and entry for three years. Furthermore, persons receive a blue identification card for the duration of their initially temporary residence (HELPgv, 2018a). If asylum is not granted, applicants can also receive the status of subsidiary protection, meaning that a return to the country of origin would present a threat to the applicant's life and integrity due to prevalent violence of war or conflict (Art 2. ECHR, Art. 3. ECHR) (Limberger, 2017: 182). Holders of subsidiary protection are entitled to a temporary residence of one year and are issued a grey Card for Persons Eligible for Subsidiary Protection (EMN, 2015: 52).

A third category of international protection titles are beneficiaries of humanitarian protection. The issuance of temporary residence permits can be based on humanitarian considerations that generally apply to persons who cannot be returned long term due to a number of reasons. Most often, this concerns the preservation of family units or so-called hardship cases (*Härtefälle*) that display a high level of integration (BFA, 2014). It can, however, also be granted under consideration of a need for 'particular protection', meaning that a person is either a victim of or witness to human trafficking, has been a victim of violence in his/her family or that his/her forced return has been de facto suspended for more than one year (Unternehmensservice-Portal, 2018). In these cases, an ordinary residence permit, a Residence Permit for Individual Protection or a Residence Permit Plus is issued (each for the duration of one year). While the first two titles require an authorization as stipulated under the Federal Act on the Employment of Foreigners, the latter as such entitles persons to pursue employment.

Upon granting asylum or subsidiary protection family reunification can be conducted under certain conditions. Regarding both beneficiaries of asylum and subsidiary protection, family

members can address an Austrian consular authority abroad in order to apply for a visa. This option is not only conditioned by time limits (the family member needs to apply within the first three months of asylum or after three years of subsidiary protection) but entails further criteria that apply to beneficiaries of subsidiary protection in general and to persons granted asylum whose family member lodged the application after the three-month deadline. In these cases, the beneficiaries of protection titles need to account for an 'adequate accommodation', health insurance as well as sufficient income (HELPgv, 2018b).

A positive outcome of the asylum procedure means that persons drop out of Basic Welfare Support and are transferred to the general social aid system. At its core is a Needs-Based Minimum Benefit that falls entirely into the competences of the provinces. It is provided for persons who have personal savings of no more than 4,189 EUR (2016), enjoy legal residence in Austria and are available for employment. Until 2016, services were standardized with an average of 844 EUR, yet since the expiration of a harmonizing agreement between the federal government and provinces, standards have diverged increasingly (Table 8).

Table 8: General provisions for beneficiaries of asylum and subsidiary protection on Needs-Based Minimum Benefit: single households and single parents

	Basic allowance	Conditions and limitations
Burgenland	584 EUR	- 1.500 EUR household limit (annulled by VfGH on 7.3. 2018) - cuts of 30% upon violation of integration obligations - cuts of 50 % upon violation of AMS obligations
Lower Austria	572 EUR	- 1.500 EUR household limit (annulled by VfGH on 7.3. 2018) - obligation to participate in integration courses - AMS related obligations (incl. obligation to take on non-profit work)
Vienna	844 EUR	- obligation to participate in integration courses - AMS related obligations (cuts between 25-50 % for one month upon violation)
Upper Austria	520 EUR	- 1.500 EUR household limit (annulled by VfGH on 7.3.2018) - 155 EUR basic allowance amount is determined by fulfillment of integration obligations
Styria	863 EUR	- 628 EUR are provided in cash, the rest are in-kind allowances - obligation to participate in integration courses - AMS related obligations (cuts of up to 25 % upon violation)
Carinthia	844 EUR	- obligation to participate in integration courses
Tyrol	647 EUR	- obligation to participate in integration courses (cuts of up to 66% upon violation) - 485 EUR for persons living in a shared flat
Salzburg	844 EUR	- obligation to participate in integration courses
Vorarlberg	645 EUR	- obligation to participate in integration courses - 482 EUR for persons living in a shared flat

Sources: ORF Wien, 2017; Wiener Zeitung, 2017; Sozialministerium, 2018; Salzburg24, 2017.

In 2017, the Needs-Based Minimum Benefit was also tied to the participation in integration programmes in most provinces. Since late 2017, persons granted asylum or subsidiary protection after 21st of December 2014 and above the age of 15 are obliged to participate in institutionally embedded integration measures. Those are mainly covered by the recent Integration Act (IntG) and Integration Year Act (IJG). As was mentioned in the subchapter 'Regular migration', the IntG stipulates a duty to integration that includes a compulsory attendance to language courses and 'value and orientation' courses upon the acquisition of a title. German classes are provided by the BMEIA up to a level of A1 and implemented by the ÖIF, while level A2 classes are offered by the BMASK and implemented by the AMS. Value and orientation courses are also provided by the BMEIA and the ÖIF, targeting the communication of constitutional and democratic principles, rules of peaceful public life and values such as self-

determination and equality. In the long run, the goal of these measures is the acquisition of the Austrian citizenship (§ 2, IntG).

The IJG defines more narrowly the provisions on the first year of beneficiaries of asylum and subsidiary protection but it also considers asylum applicants. The purpose is to rapidly assess relevant professional skills and facilitate inclusion into the labour market for those who could not find a job. The mentioned courses are structured as modules and the progress has to be protocolled within an integration booklet. Asylum applicants may only participate if they belong to a group '[...] where the granting of international protection is very likely under consideration of prevalent data [...]' (translated from German: § 1, IJG).

Furthermore, persons are entitled to child care and family subsidies. Health insurance is provided for gainful workers whose wage is above the monthly limit of 438 EUR (in 2018). In addition, persons receiving Needs-Based Minimum Benefit are entitled to be insured within their respective province.

Regarding housing, beneficiaries of international protection are allowed to take residency at any province and have open access to the housing market. As many persons rely on social aid, which varies across provinces but remains comparably low compared to rental prices, they can apply for housing aid. Generally, these persons are equal to citizens in this regard; however, conditions are generally in favour of the latter. In Vienna, for example, persons must have had an earned income for at least one year and beneficiaries of asylum are only entitled to aid after five years. Tyrol and Upper Austria also hold provisions for a minimum of five years of residence; Vorarlberg requires full-time employment (Aslywohnung.at, 2018).

Renewal and naturalisation

Cases of asylum are reviewed after three years. Unless provisions for residence terminating measures or a withdrawal of status apply, the persons are eligible for unlimited settlement by means of a Permanent Residence – EU title after a total five year of residence in Austria and the fulfilment of the integration criteria. Holders of subsidiary protection who initially have a residence permit of one year might receive a two-year extension, which can also lead to an entitlement to permanent residence under the same conditions (HELPgv, 2018c). Persons who have received a residence permit of one year resulting from humanitarian considerations can only renew their title if they are holders of a Residence Permit for Individual Protection (EMN, 2015: 54). Like the other two groups, these persons can also solidify their legal residence after five years legally spent in Austria. Persons with a regular residence permit and those with a Residence Permit Plus can validate their entire time while those with a Residence Permit for Individual Protection can only validate half of their annual terms (HELPgv, 2018c).

The pathway to citizenship¹¹ for recognized refugees is shorter than the general provision of ten years of legal residence. Accordingly, beneficiaries of asylum may apply for citizenship after six years of continuous residence and only if no withdrawal procedure has been initiated

¹¹ The Citizenship Law (311/1985) stipulates the jus sanguinis principle and does not allow dual citizenship, unless an Austrian born person has parents with different citizenship. After ten years of residence, persons are generally eligible for citizenship, however they need to fulfill conditions such as the acquisition of German (level B1), knowledge about the history of Austria and no criminal record. Beneficiaries of asylum have a legal claim to citizenship after six years of residence, yet the same conditions apply here as well.

(EMN, 2015: 56). Holders of subsidiary protection and those with a humanitarian title do not benefit from these special regulations; they fall under general provisions, stipulating a minimum of ten years of legal residence of which five years need to be spent under settlement (MSNO, 2015).

Table 9: Overview of important rights and duties for applicants of international protection and upon a positive outcome

	Status	Rights/ Guarantees	Duties
Stage I: Admissibility procedure	Tolerated (Green Procedure Card)	- Protection from forced return	- Cooperation - Stay within municipality
Stage II: Substantive procedure	Asylum applicant (White Card for Temporary Residence)	- Basic Welfare Support - Health insurance - Access to housing market - Only charitable work or apprenticeship	- Cooperation - Place of residence within the province of Basic Welfare Support
Stage III: Positive decision	Beneficiary of Asylum (Convention passport)	- 3 years of legal residence - Social Insurance (including Needs-Based Minimum Benefit and health insurance) - Access to labour market	- Civic integration programs
	Subsidiary Protection (Grey Card for Persons Eligible for Subsidiary Protection)	- 1 year of legal residence - Social Insurance (including Needs-Based Minimum Benefit and health insurance) - Access to labour market	- Civic integration programs
	Humanitarian title (for example, Residence Permit Plus)	- 1 year of legal residence - Social Insurance (including Needs-Based Minimum Benefit and health insurance) - Access to labour market	- Civic integration programs

Source: own compilation.

5.3 Losing the right to reside in the country: negative decision, cessation, withdrawal

In the immediate context of international protection, the termination of a legal residence or a tolerated stay in Austria can generally be initiated following a negative decision in the admissibility procedure as it is mentioned in the Dublin procedure. Secondly, it may accompany a negative decision in the substantive procedure or upon reviewing a case.

If a person is denied a title to international protection or if a title expires and reasons for granting asylum or subsidiary protection are no longer given, the decision of the BFA is usually accompanied by a return decision. Persons are subsequently obliged to cooperate on their return, which usually receives a time limit of 14 days (a suspension of the time limit might be acquired on request). Voluntary return implies that the persons returning can apply to have their costs for transportation and the delivery of documents covered (BFA, 2018b). This amounts to a maximum of 1,000 EUR for the first 1,000 applicants based on an initiative of

2016/2017 (BFA, 2018c). Since late 2017, persons with a final negative decision are required to move to a specific Basic Welfare Support accommodation, where they are prepared for their return (Knapp, 2017).

In some cases, legal return consultation through the VMÖ can be compulsory even prior to a decision, namely if a negative decision is considered in advance (§ 52a Section 2 BFA-VG; cited in: Lukits, 2016, p.18). Likewise, restrictions to stay within a municipality or even within a given facility (HELPGv, 2017) can be imposed on persons who reside within a Basic Welfare Support accommodation provided by the federal government and who do not cooperate. If a person does not voluntarily return to the country of origin or if an immediate expulsion is necessary, authorities may enact a forced return. This requires a passport or a return certificate from the respective embassy. Following diplomatic difficulties regarding the issuance of according papers, the 2017 Aliens Law Amendment Act (145/2017) created a provision that allows BFA authorities to mandate persons for a self-instructed application (§ 46 Section 2 FPG 2005). Upon the acquisition of these documents, a forced return is carried out separately or with charter machines, often under Frontex Joint Return Operations. Since 2017, authorities are no longer obligated to communicate the date of the expulsion (Knapp, 2017: 31). Persons are allowed to receive Basic Welfare Support until the completion of a return, though services are partly curtailed if persons do not cooperate.

A third instance that generally leads to a termination of residence and a return order is when the status for beneficiaries of international protection is withdrawn. A withdrawal procedure can be initiated following the move of a person's main place of residence outside of Austria or when a person returns to the country of origin (EMN, 2015: 53). Additionally, § 6 of the AsylG 2005 stipulates a withdrawal when a person constitutes a threat to public order and safety or when a person commits a crime.¹² If such an aggravated crime occurs, criminal prosecution and the withdrawal procedure are initiated separately. While in previous years the latter could only be started following a legal conviction, the 2017 Aliens Law Amendment Act (145/2017) now allows for a withdrawal procedure right after a legal charge (§ 27 Section 2 AsylG 2005). Upon a conviction, the prison sentence is served in Austria and a forced return is carried out afterwards (DerStandard, 2016). However, in all cases of return decisions authorities might be confronted with a legal or factual impossibility of deportation, which usually leads to a toleration status.

Between 2011 and 2014, return decisions automatically resulted in an entry ban of 18 months. However, following an appeal before the VwGH (2012/18/0029), provisions in the FPG were changed in 2013 in order to conform to the EU Return Directive. As a consequence, entry bans of 5 years are now possible depending on a person's previous behaviour regarding public order and safety. A maximum entry ban of 10 years can be ordered upon a serious threat to public order and safety, and it can also be made unlimited. The latter case applies, for example, to persons who have been convicted to more than 5 years of prison or who have joined a criminal or terrorist group (Rutz, 2014: 20).

¹² This usually applies to sentences of 3 years or more (DiePresse, 2016). Such crimes do not, for example, cover theft but they encompass robbery or rape, arguably delicts that are tied to physical assault or murder.

Stipulated under § 53 of the FPG 2005, entry bans are inherently tied to return decisions and consecutive residence terminating measures under Austrian law (Rutz, 2014: 9). Following this condition, authorities are bound to consider the private and family life of aliens prior to their decision as well as all provisions associated with the residence terminating measures for the purpose of forcibly returning the person to the country of origin. This means that entry bans cannot be ordered if family, health or social reasons prevent a return. While any third country national can receive a return decision upon very serious offences, persons with no legal residence or a negative decision on international protection qualify as such for a return decision and they also qualify for an entry ban, if they violate the provisions on voluntary return. However, entry bans cannot be ordered in cases where persons are merely returned to another EU member state. A decision of the BFA can be appealed before the BVwG, usually within only two weeks, and persons are not allowed to bring forward new evidence (Rutz, 2014: 38p.).

Detention

Aliens can furthermore be held in detention for a number of reasons that are strongly linked to their presence on Austrian territory. Arguably, this form of imprisonment is not conceptualized as punishment but as a measure of safeguarding administrative acts that are mainly related to the termination of legal stay and to guaranteeing a forced return. Aside from the EU Return and Reception Conditions Directive as well as the Dublin Regulation, provisions on detention are stipulated in the FPG. The grounds for detaining asylum applicants are therein firstly formulated as discretionary options that are conditioned by prior return decisions of the applicant, by Austria's (non-)responsibility for the case under the terms of the Dublin Regulation or by an enforceable but not final return decision. Secondly, a directory provision concerns safeguarding procedures, for example, upon violating the duty to report, not cooperating in measures for terminating residence or leaving the Initial Reception Centre without permission (EMN, 2014: 10pp.). Minors can only be held in detention from the age of 14 or higher. Authorities are generally required to check how far a measure can be considered appropriate and consequently seek more moderate solutions. This might be the ordinance to remain in an accommodation, to regularly notify a police station or to lodge a financial deposit at a police authority (EMN, 2014: 17). Considering a certain level of discretion, the Constitutional Court ruled in 2007 that the related statement of facts has to strike a balance in each individual case between considerations of public interest in safeguarding a procedure (safety and public order) and the personal freedom of the party concerned (VfSlg 18.145/2007; cited in: Feik, 2016: 168).

Following the administrative decision, the detention needs to be carried out within 14 days, during which time the detained person can address the BVwG as the appeal body. Likewise, detained persons are entitled to a free legal consultation, usually carried out by the VMÖ. The duration of detention is set to a maximum of three months for minors between 14 and 18 and six months for adults. In 2017, the provisions were further expanded to include grounds upon which detention can be prolonged to a maximum of 18 months stipulated by the EU Return Directive. Reasons for this length of detention can be a refusal to offer identification for the delivery of travel documents, the lack of approval documents for the journey, obstructing the police authorities in the course of doing their duty or intentionally setting technical obstacles for the return. Austrian detention infrastructure consists of a total of eight long-term facilities

and seven small facilities (including the Vienna Airport transit zone) that can detain persons for up to 40 days (Global-Detention-Project, 2018).

Suspended return and toleration

A return decision often does not automatically result in its execution as legal, technical or policy-related obstacles can intervene. Aside from the lack of relevant travel documents and the aforementioned legal obstacles concerning family units and personal integrity, health problems of the person to be deported or technical defaults in the transfer can also occur.

Non-removed (or tolerated) persons can accordingly receive a toleration card in order to verify their identity and to bind them to legal obligations, which, in turn, is argued to reduce the risk of abscondence. Arguably, despite or, in fact, precisely because of attempts to avoid a high politicization of this group, non-removed persons possess rights which are often overlooked by the officials¹³ (Rosenberger & Küffner, 2016: 147). They continue to be entitled to basic welfare provisions if there is no personal negligence of return and can remain in the employment position if they have previously acquired a work permit. Children are allowed to continue going to school; however, persons are no longer entitled to participate in integration programmes (Lukits, 2016a: 29). After one year of toleration it is possible to lodge an application for residence due to ‘particular protection’, which is valid for 12 months and allows for unlimited access to the labour market. Furthermore, provisions allow for a consecutive application for a Red-White-Red Card Plus, which is granted under conditions that take into account the length of stay, the integration level as well as participation in the labour market (BFA, 2014).

5.4 Undocumented migrants

The first category of undocumented migrants¹⁴ are persons who are entitled to legal entry and stay but do not register at any responsible authority. These can be tourists staying in non-commercial accommodations or EU citizens who do not register their place of residence. Unless they are registered, persons residing in Austria for an extended time period cannot apply for social aid services or child care or open a bank account, to name a few (Fassmann, 2015).

The second group of undocumented migrants are third country nationals whose presence within Austrian territory is irregular, meaning that they are not in possession of legal documents allowing for entry or stay. These can be third country nationals entering without a residence permit or a visa, persons overstaying their visa or persons who have entered the country via the asylum system. It has to be noted that applying for asylum in Austria (apart from family reunification) is inevitably tied to a legal limbo time period within the federal territory, as applications can generally not be lodged at diplomatic outposts. According to a standard form stipulated in the Schengen Borders Code entry can be refused through a decision that states the concise reasons. Since Austria generally only holds permanent border control posts at

¹³ Official statistics on the number of people receiving a toleration card show great discrepancies compared to the gap between persons with a return order and the number of persons actually transferred.

¹⁴ These statistics that are based on criminal records and assume an equal share of irregular migrants among criminal suspects and the entire residential population estimated between 65,000 and 183,000 undocumented migrants in Austria in 2014 (Fassmann, 2015).

international airports and since legal or practical obstacles to an immediate return upon irregular entry are possible, it is important to consider that the authorities are allowed to order persons to remain in certain places (Kratzmann & Adel-Naim, 2012: 28-29).

Austrian law does not have any explicit rights concerning undocumented migrants but since human rights provisions apply to all persons within a territory independent of their legal status those migrants have access to medical care in case of an emergency and children are allowed to enter the formal education system. However, they cannot access the formal labour or housing market.

Apart from return, there are two major regularization pathways in Austria. The first one leads to a residence title such as the Settlement Permit or the Red-White-Red Card Plus, providing the person has established his/her private or family life in Austria according to Art. 8 ECHR or has, in addition to that, fulfilled the first module of the Integration Agreement (Kratzmann & Adel-Naim, 2012: 32). The second pathway can depart from the status of toleration due to obstacles to return or a residence permit issued on humanitarian grounds following an asylum procedure and can lead to a Residence Permit Plus. This permit is valid for one year and makes it possible, for example, to register for a place of residence and to access the labour market. A system of residence solidification, referred to as *Aufenthaltsverfestigung*, which is inherent to the entirety of provisions under the NAG 2005 increases the protection from removal parallel to the duration of stay, acquisition of the German language or the development of private and family ties (EMN, 2005). General amnesties for irregular migrants have been very rare in Austrian history due to a high scepticism regarding potential pull effects (Kratzmann & Adel-Naim, 2012: 57).

6 Refugee crisis driven reforms since 2015

The perception of a refugee crisis in Austria grew since the beginning of summer 2015, when increasingly large numbers of refugees arrived in clustered groups. An estimated 600,000 persons crossed Austria as a transit country in that year and 88,340 persons lodged an application for international protection (MSNO, 2016). At first, the increasingly congested Initial Reception Centre in Traiskirchen, the train stations and later the border crossing points were supported by a strong engagement of the civil society. Later referred to as ‘welcome culture’, socioeconomic, cultural and political initiatives for refugees emerged in the light of insufficient action of institutional and political actors. While this engagement quickly professionalized into emerging NGOs¹⁵, broader societal support declined and in part even turned into rejection over time (Müller & Rosenberger, 2017: 118). By September 2015, the federal government, led by an SPÖ chancellor and an ÖVP interior minister, had reintroduced systematic border controls and installed two Refugee Coordinators, who were responsible for organizing permanent accommodation facilities. Border management on the one hand and the distribution of persons and reception responsibilities on the other remained two central political concerns in the following months.

Concerning borders, the federal government successfully negotiated prolongations of a Schengen suspension with the Commission. It was then able to terminate the initial passing-through strategy as well as erect a border fence with Slovenia by early 2016. Although left empty, the attached facility system with tents and provisional sanitary devices continues to be sustained to this day. Aside from unilateral measures, the issue of border management was also tackled at the international level. In February 2016, Austrian officials seized the Western Balkans Summit for administrative and financial cooperation on policing prominent migratory routes between Greece and central European states.¹⁶

With regard to the distribution of asylum applicants on the national level, the federal government introduced the Federal Constitutional Act for the Accommodation and Distribution of Foreigners in Need of Help and Protection (120/2015) that enables it to enforce accommodation space in municipalities if the provinces do not fulfil the quotas. Concerning the relocation of refugees from the Hotspots in Greece and Italy, federal authorities displayed great resistance despite an Austrian approval in the Council. The Austrian chancellor tried to avoid the admission of 1,952 asylum applicants through a letter to the EU Commission stating how Austria had already admitted a disproportional amount of refugees.¹⁷

¹⁵ Newly emerging NGOs and initiatives like ‘Train of Hope’, ‘Happy.Thankyou.Moreplease!!’ or ‘Fremde werden Freunde’ compensated for state deficits in the realm of reception, coordination, and integration according to Simsa et al. (2016). They did not only contribute to a so-called ‘welcome culture’, but also provided important mediating structures. Yet, early scholarly policy recommendations such as the one by Simsa et al. (2016) urging for a proper public funding and institutional cooperation with these initiatives have largely been disregarded as of 2018.

¹⁶ The non-invitation of Greek authorities led to temporary diplomatic tensions between Greece and Austria (DerStandard, 2016b).

¹⁷ By January 2018, the government ended up admitting 43 persons from Italy (DiePresse, 2017a; DiePresse, 2018).

By the end of 2015, the federal government initiated a series of legal reforms that were adopted in May 2016. The 2016 Amendment Act (24/2016) introduced modifications to the AsylG 2005, the FPG 2005 and the BFA-VG 2012. According to Knapp (2016a) the most important legal changes encompass:

- the possibility to act upon an emergency decree if the number of asylum applicants reaches a level that threatens public order and security, allowing authorities to temporarily suspend the processing of further applications (Section 5 §36 and §41 AsylG),
- a general confinement of the entitlement to asylum for three years upon which each case is reviewed (§3 AsylG),
- extended decision periods for BFA authorities from 6 to 15 months for the duration of 2 years (§22 AsylG),
- time limits for family reunification: in the first three weeks upon a family member's acquisition of an asylum status or after three years for beneficiaries of subsidiary protection (§35 AsylG),
- identification cards for asylum beneficiaries (§51a AsylG),
- obligatory contact with the ÖIF for beneficiaries of asylum and subsidiary protection (§67a AsylG).

Furthermore, an amendment of the FPG allowed for extended detention periods of 14 days (previously 120 hours) for the purpose of preparing a return (§39 FPG) as well as the use of video conferences for translation tasks during the admissibility procedure (amendment of the BFA Proceedings Act).

By the end of 2017, a second series of amendments was implemented. Legal reforms under the 2017 Aliens Law Amendment Act (145/2017) involved changes in the NAG 2005, the FPG 2005, the AsylG 2005, the BFA-VG 2012, the GVG-B 2005 and the GrekoG 1996, some of which include (according to Knapp, 2016b):

- the possibility of ordering house detention in the Basic Welfare Support facility for delinquent asylum applicants or persons coming from safe third countries,
- a confinement of the registered place of residence for asylum applicants to the province they were assigned to within their Basic Welfare Support and sanctions of 100 to 1,000 EUR upon violation,
- the possibility to order persons with a residence terminating decision to stay in an accommodation of the federal government and sanctions of 100 to 1,000 EUR upon violation,
- increased detention periods from previously 10 months to a new maximum of 18 months,
- extended decision periods for the BVwG from 6 to 12 months until May 2018.

Aside from these provisions on the asylum procedure, the integration of aliens and the public threat they potentially posed became highly debated political topics. The Integration Act (IntG) (68/2017) introduced an obligation for aliens to actively cooperate in the integration process. Persons granted asylum or subsidiary protection now need to sign an integration declaration that obligates them to take value and orientation courses as well as German classes. This is a considerable step, as these groups had previously been excluded from language and civic integration obligations stipulated for migrants under the NAG (EMN, 2015: 53). Non-

participation can lead to sanctions on social aid provisions in most of the provinces. The Integration Year Act (IJG), furthermore, entails provisions on asylum applicants ‘with a high probability of approval’ and focuses on the integration of these groups into the labour market as a gateway to societal inclusion. It stipulates an integration program of at least one year which evaluates competences and provides a number of courses. In doing so, it is tightly associated with the Approval and Assessment Act (AuBG) (55/2016) that sets up a framework for the assessment and approval criteria of professional qualifications.

The same legal package also includes the Anti-Face-Covering Act (68/2017), which prohibits the wearing of clothes or other objects that might hide or conceal facial features in public places or buildings. This measure has been openly declared as a symbolic act for an ‘open society’ (BMEIA, 2018).

Against the background of an increasingly polarized public opinion on the topics of immigration and asylum, new dynamics in party politics have evolved. Debates within the parties and tensions between the partners of the grand coalition have led to a reorganization of the federal government staff as an immediate response to the public discontent over how this perceived crisis is being dealt with. Upon the accession of a new SPÖ chancellor and ÖVP interior minister, the government continued to pursue a restrictive course, and yet support for the right-wing FPÖ was growing. With the FPÖ benefiting from a decades-long issue ownership and the ÖVP presenting the former foreign minister as the lead candidate with increasing anti-immigration positions at the 2017 national elections, these two parties maximized their share of votes successfully. While the FPÖ entered the government, the party with the most liberal stances on immigration and asylum, namely the Green Party, experienced a negative impact of these topics on their result. Together with internal conflicts and a party split, this led to the party dropping out of the National Council after 31 years.

7 Conclusion

Austria has a long tradition of being a destination country for migrants and refugees, a country that for decades promoted labour migration and admitted refugees during the communist era of Eastern Europe as well as during the time of the Balkan Wars. The notion of the latest advent of mass migration to Austria relates to the increasing number of asylum applications since 2013 and in particular in 2015. In that year alone, application numbers reached a six-decade high of 88,340 persons, while thousands of others crossed federal territory for their onward journey. Besides the quantity and frequency of immigration, this latest phase also displays novelties concerning the composition of the newcomers in terms of countries of origin. Arguably, the three largest groups of asylum applicants in 2015, namely Syrians, Afghans and Iraqis, are relatively new to Austria, with their numbers increasing by 1,265 per cent, 430 per cent, and 232 per cent respectively between 2011 and 2017.

Lawmakers reacted to these latest developments by introducing a series of legislative reforms that are shaping the consecutive and future developments of asylum and migration. While Austria displays a comparatively high level of standards concerning international protection, it is difficult to assess the impact of the latest fast-paced reforms. On the one hand, reception facilities were expanded, creating new capacities and co-ordination structures that improved the previously highly critical overcrowding of the Initial Reception Centre Traiskirchen (Volksanwaltschaft, 2015). Likewise, additional civic integration measures were created for beneficiaries of international protection which were supplemented by broad local civil society and NGO involvement. The federal overall policy goal however, aimed at reducing the number of newcomers in the long run. In 2016, the entitlement to asylum was accordingly limited initially to three years and family reunification was restrained through application time limits. The federal government also introduced a unilateral annual quota for asylum applications that allows for acting upon an emergency decree and suspending further processing of applications upon exhaustion. While application figures have not reached the according limits by 2018, legal experts (Obwexer, 2016) have been highly critical, pointing out how preventing of persons from lodging an application to international protection would violate human rights, EU and constitutional laws. Thus, a de facto implementation of the annual quota provision has to be awaited. In addition, Austria has been conducting systematic border controls along certain checkpoints, thereby repeatedly extending Schengen exemption provisions. In 2017, further reforms particularly aimed at tightening duties for asylum applicants and persons with final negative decisions, as well as setting up integration duties that also work as means to obtain social services in their full extent.

Apart from state internal conflicts, border management and the distribution of refugees from Hotspots became highly contested issues in Austria's relationship to other EU member states. The notion of porous external borders, Austria's geopolitical position in the middle of the Schengen Area and its high admission rate in 2015 led to a resistant stance on the EU-wide distribution despite the political approval and the search for non-EU state alliances in the transnational policing of borders along the Western Balkan Route.

While the principle of asylum is deeply embedded in the Austrian constitution and European Union law, the governance of immigration and asylum has in recent years been repeatedly impeded by the Constitutional Court (VfGH), which intervened in both federal and provincial laws that aimed at restricting refugee's rights and entitlements. First and foremost, this relates to the federal government's attempts of rendering asylum procedures more efficient

while decreasing the effectiveness of legal remedies. The VfGH annulled provisions that tightened appeal periods and urged the reparation of appeal regulations for persons in detention. Likewise, it repeatedly ruled in favour of private and family life needs during family asylum procedures. The VfGH did thereby not only address violations of fundamental rights along a procedural dimension, but also touched upon material asylum law. For example, it ruled that women with a western-oriented lifestyle could validate this as a ground for international protection, even if the lifestyle had been adopted in the host country.

Aside from federal legislation, the Court has also addressed increasingly restrictive social welfare provisions by the provinces of Upper Austria and Lower Austria. Accordingly, attempts of a general attachment of the Needs-Based Minimum Benefit to the length of residence and size of households were annulled. Austrian provinces have not only chosen diverging paths in the realm of social aid services, but also displayed discrepancies regarding reception quotas for asylum applicants. This turned into a major site of conflict during the crisis. The fulfilment of admission quotas and the provision of allowances and accommodation facilities was debated alongside matters of financial resources, social aid deservingness and cultural or identity-based issues, and it resulted in the creation of a federal constitutional law allowing the federal instalment of reception facilities, even against the will of the provinces and municipalities.

Finally, it was not only the state and its institutions that affected the life of immigrants and refugees, the so-called ‘refugee crisis’ has doubtlessly also had an impact on the Austrian political landscape. It was a top priority topic on the political agenda paired with strong public opinions. Accordingly, in the wake of the crisis, the federal government underwent a reconfiguration with party internal exchanges of prominent figures such as the interior minister and the chancellor in early 2016. During the national elections of 2017, asylum and migration remained highly salient topics. The major winning parties were the right-wing FPÖ, which had had a strong ownership of the issue for decades, and the conservative ÖVP, whose lead candidate had previously been foreign minister and had particularly pushed an agenda for order and security.

Appendices

Glossary and list of abbreviations

Abbrevia- tion	German	English
AGesVG	Anti-Gesichtsverhüllungsgesetz	Anti-Face-Covering Act
AMS	Arbeitsmarktservice	Public Employment Service
AsylG	Asylgesetz	Asylum Act
AuBG	Anerkennungs- und Bewertungsgesetz	Approval and Assessment Act
BFA	Bundesamt für Fremdenwesen und Asyl	Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum
BFA-VG	BFA-Verfahrensgesetz	BFA-Proceedings Act
BMASK	Bundesministerium für Arbeit, Soziales, Gesundheit und Konsumentenschutz	Federal Ministry for Labour, Social Affairs and Consumer Protection
BMEIA	Bundesministerium für Europa, Integration und Äußeres	Federal Ministry for Europe, Integration and Foreign Affairs
BM.I	Bundesministerium für Inneres	Federal Ministry of Internal Affairs
BVwG	Bundesverwaltungsgericht	Federal Administrative Court
EAST	Erstaufnahmestelle	Initial Reception Centre
FPG	Fremdenpolizeigesetz	Aliens Police Act
GrekoG	Grenzkontrollgesetz	Border Control Act
IJG	Integrationsjahrgesetz	Integration Year Act
IntG	Integrationsgesetz	Integration Act
NAG	Niederlassungs- und Aufenthaltsgesetz	Settlement and Residence Act
OGH	Oberster Gerichtshof	Supreme Court of Justice
ÖIF	Österreichischer Integrationsfonds	Austrian Integration Fund
VA	Volksanwaltschaft	Austrian Ombudsman Board
VMÖ	Verein Menschenrechte Österreich	Human Rights Group Austria
VfGH	Verfassungsgerichtshof	Constitutional Court
VwGH	Verwaltungsgerichtshof	Administrative High Court

Annex I: Overview of the legal framework on migration, asylum and reception conditions

Legislation title (original and English) and number	Date	Type of law	Object	Link/ PDF
Bundesgesetz über die Niederlassung und den Aufenthalt in Österreich (Niederlassungs- und Aufenthaltsgesetz – NAG) Federal Act concerning the Settlement and Residence in Austria (NAG)	StF: BGBl Nr. 100/2005	Law	Permission and withdrawal of legal residence and settlement permits	RIS
Bundesgesetz über die Gewährung von Asyl (AsylG) Federal Act concerning the Granting of Asylum	StF: BGBl. I Nr. 100/2005	Law	Asylum applicants and beneficiaries of international protection: criteria on entry, identification, qualification, asylum procedure and return	RIS
Bundesgesetz über die Ausübung der Fremdenpolizei, die Ausstellung von Dokumenten für Fremde und die Erteilung von Einreisetiteln (FPG) Federal Act on the Exercise of Aliens' Police, the Issue of Documents for Aliens and the Granting of Entry Permits	Stf: BGBl. I NR. 100/2005	Law	Aliens' entrance to federal territory, grounds for rejection, residence terminating measures, return, toleration and the issuance of documents for foreigners	RIS
Bundesgesetz, mit dem die allgemeinen Bestimmungen über das Verfahren vor dem Bundesamt für Fremdenwesen und Asyl zur Gewährung von internationalem Schutz, Erteilung von Aufenthaltstiteln aus berücksichtigungswürdigen Gründen, Abschiebung, Duldung und zur Erlassung von aufenthaltsbeendenden Maßnahmen sowie zur Ausstellung von österreichischen Dokumenten für Fremde geregelt werden (BFA-Verfahrensgesetz – BFA-VG) Federal Act on the general rules for procedures at the federal office for immigration and asylum for the granting of international protection, the issuing of residence permits due to extenuating circumstances, deportation, tolerated stay and issuing of stay terminating measures, furthermore the issuing of documents for aliens. BFA Proceedings Act (BFA-VG)	StF: BGBl. I Nr. 87/2012	Law	Procedures for application to international protection, return, toleration and residence terminating measures	RIS

<p>Bundesgesetz über die Einrichtung und Organisation des Bundesamtes für Fremdenwesen und Asyl (BFA-Einrichtungsgesetz – BFA-G)</p> <p>Federal Act on the implementation and organization of the federal immigration and asylum office</p>	<p>StF: BGBl. I Nr. 87/ 2012</p>	<p>Law</p>	<p>Institutional framework concerning organization and functioning of the BFA</p>	<p>RIS</p>
<p>Vereinbarung zwischen dem Bund und den Ländern gemäß Art. 15a B-VG über gemeinsame Maßnahmen zur vorübergehenden Grundversorgung für hilfs- und schutzbedürftige Fremde (Asylwerber, Asylberechtigte, Vertriebene und andere aus rechtlichen oder faktischen Gründen nicht abschiebbare Menschen) in Österreich</p> <p>Agreement of 15 July 2004 between the federal state and the provinces under Article 15a of the Federal Constitution concerning joint action for the temporary Basic Welfare Support of aliens in need of help and protection in Austria</p>	<p>StF: BGBl. I Nr. 80/ 2004</p>	<p>Agreement based on constitutional law</p>	<p>Division of competences of Basic Welfare Support during substantive procedure and distribution of asylum applicants across provinces</p>	<p>RIS</p>
<p>Bundesgesetz, mit dem die Grundversorgung von Asylwerbern im Zulassungsverfahren und bestimmten anderen Fremden geregelt wird (GVG-B)</p> <p>Federal Act to regulate the Basic Welfare Support of asylum applicants in the admission procedure and of certain other foreigners (GVG-B)</p>	<p>StF: BGBl. I Nr. 405/ 1991</p>	<p>Law</p>	<p>Basic Welfare Support during admissibility procedure</p>	<p>RIS</p>
<p>Vereinbarung zwischen dem Bund und den Ländern gemäß Artikel 15a B-VG über die Erhöhung ausgewählter Kostenhöchstsätze des Artikel 9 der Grundversorgungsvereinbarung</p> <p>Agreement between the federal state and states under Article 15a of the Basic Care Act concerning the raise of selected maximum cost rates of Article 9 Basic Welfare Support Agreement</p> <p>Amended by:</p> <p>Agreement between the federal state and states under Article 15a concerning the raise</p>	<p>StF: BGBl. I 46/ 2013</p> <p>StF: BGBl 48/ 2016</p>	<p>Agreement based on constitutional law</p>	<p>Increase of maximum expenses on Basic Welfare Support</p>	<p>RIS</p>

of selected maximum cost rates of Article 9 Basic Welfare Support Agreement				
<p>Bundesverfassungsgesetz für die Unterbringung und Aufteilung von hilfs- und schutzbedürftigen Fremden</p> <p>Federal Constitutional Act for the accommodation and distribution of foreigners in need of help and protection</p>	StF: BGBl 120/2015	Constitutional law	Availability of accommodation for the purpose of Basic Welfare Support within municipalities (according to a quota) and the right of the federal government to enforce accommodation space within its own properties	RIS
<p>Bundesgesetz über die Durchführung von Personenkontrollen aus Anlass des Grenzübertritts (GrekoG)</p> <p>Federal Act concerning the implementation of identity checks at the instance of border crossings (GrekoG)</p>	StF: BGBl 435/1996	Law	Border facilities and border controls	RIS
<p>Bundesgesetz, mit dem ein Integrationsgesetz (IntG) und ein Anti-Gesichtsverhüllungsgesetz (AGesVG) erlassen sowie das Niederlassungs- und Aufenthaltsgesetz, das Asylgesetz 2005, das Fremdenpolizeigesetz 2005, das Staatsbürgerschaftsgesetz 1985 und die Straßenverkehrsordnung 1960 geändert werden.</p> <p>Federal Act on the enactment of an integration law and anti-face-covering law (IntG, AGesVG)</p>	StF: BGBl 68/2017	Law	Obligation to participation in civic integration courses and ban on public wearing of face-covering clothes	BGBl
<p>Bundesgesetz zur Arbeitsmarktintegration von arbeitsfähigen Asylberechtigten und subsidiär Schutzberechtigten sowie AsylwerberInnen, bei denen die Zuerkennung des internationalen Schutzes wahrscheinlich ist, im Rahmen eines Integrationsjahres (Integrationsjahrgesetz – IJG)</p> <p>Federal Act on labour market integration of beneficiaries of asylum and subsidiary protection, as well as asylum applicants, who are likely to receive international protection as part of an integration year (IJG)</p>	StF: BGBl. I Nr. 75/2017	Law	Labour market integration of beneficiaries of asylum and subsidiary protection, as well as specific asylum applicants	RIS

<p>Bundesgesetz über die Vereinfachung der Verfahren zur Anerkennung und Bewertung ausländischer Bildungsabschlüsse und Berufsqualifikationen (Anerkennungs- und Bewertungsgesetz – AuBG)</p> <p>Federal Act on the simplification of procedures for the accreditation and evaluation of foreign education and qualification certificates (AuBG)</p>	<p>Stf: BGBl. I Nr. 55/ 2016</p>	<p>Law</p>	<p>Education and qualification certificates for integration into the labour market and education system</p>	<p>RIS</p>
<p>Bundesgesetz über die österreichische Staatsbürgerschaft</p> <p>Federal Act on Citizenship</p>	<p>StF: BGBl 311/ 1985</p>	<p>Law</p>	<p>Criteria for naturalisation</p>	<p>RIS</p>
<p>Verordnung der Bundesministerin für Inneres über den Beirat für die Führung der Staatendokumentation</p> <p>Ordinance of the federal minister of internal affairs concerning the advisory board on the operation of Country of Origin Information</p>	<p>StF: BGBl. II Nr. 413 /2005</p>	<p>Decree</p>		<p>RIS</p>
<p>Verordnung der Bundesregierung, mit der Staaten als sichere Herkunftsstaaten festgelegt werden</p> <p>Ordinance of the federal government, concerning the determination of countries as safe countries of origin</p>	<p>StF: BGBl. II Nr. 177/ 2009</p>	<p>Decree</p>		<p>RIS</p>
<p>Verordnung der Bundesministerin für Inneres zur Durchführung des Asylgesetzes 2005 (AsylG-DV)</p> <p>Ordinance of the federal minister of internal affairs, for the implementation of the Asylum Law 2005 (AsylG-DV)</p>	<p>StF: BGBl II Nr. 448/ 2005</p>	<p>Decree</p>		<p>RIS</p>
<p>Verordnung der Bundesministerin für Inneres, mit der das unbefugte Betreten und der unbefugte Aufenthalt in den Betreuungseinrichtungen des Bundes verboten wird 2005</p> <p>Ordinance of the federal minister of internal affairs, concerning the prohibition of unauthorised entry and stay in federal care facilities</p>	<p>StF: BGBl. II Nr. 2/ 2005</p>	<p>Decree</p>		<p>RIS</p>
<p>Verordnung der Bundesministerin für Inneres über die Anhaltung von Menschen</p>	<p>StF: BGBl. II Nr. 128/</p>	<p>Decree</p>		<p>RIS</p>

<p>durch die Sicherheitsbehörden und Organe des öffentlichen Sicherheitsdienstes Ordinance of the federal minister of internal affairs, concerning the arrest of persons by the security authorities and institutions of the public security service</p>	<p>1999</p>			
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Annex II: List of authorities involved in migration governance

Authority (English and original name)	Tier of government (national, regional, local)	Type of organization	Area of competence in the fields of migration and asylum	Link
Bundesministerium für Europa, Integration und Äußeres (BMEIA) Federal Ministry for Europe, Integration and Foreign Affairs	Federal	Ministry	Borders, immigration, emigration, return, citizenship, asylum	Link
Bundesministerium für Arbeit, Soziales, Gesundheit und Konsumentenschutz (BMAK) Federal Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs, Health and Consumer Protection	Federal	Ministry	Access to labour market, integration	Link
Bundesministerium für Inneres (BM.I) Federal Ministry of the Interior	Federal	Ministry	Visa, diplomatic services, integration	Link
Bundesamt für Fremdenwesen und Asyl (BFA) Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum	Federal	Executive body	Protection	Link
Österreichischer Integrationsfonds (ÖIF) Austrian Integration Fund	Federal	Executive body	Integration	Link
Arbeitsmarktservice (AMS) Public Employment Service	Federal	Executive body	Labour market	Link
Verfassungsgerichtshof (VfGH) Constitutional Court	Federal	Judiciary	Protection	Link
Verwaltungsgerichtshof (VwGH) Administrative High Court	Federal	Judiciary	Protection	Link
Bundesverwaltungsgericht (BVwG) Federal Administrative Court	Federal	Judiciary	Protection	Link

Fonds Soziales Wien Vienna Social Fund	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	
Koordinationsstelle für Ausländerfragen Niederösterreich Coordination Office for Aliens Affairs Lower Austria	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	
Referat Grundversorgung für Fremde Burgenland Department of Basic Welfare Support for Alien Burgenland	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	
Referat für Flüchtlingsangelegenheit Steiermark Department of Refugee Affairs Styria	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	
Referat für Flüchtlingswesen und Integration Kärnten Department of Refugee and Integration Affairs Carinthia	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	
Referat Grundversorgung für Fremde Oberösterreich Department of Basic Welfare for Aliens Upper Austria	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	
Referat Soziale Absicherung und Eingliederung Salzburg Department of Social Coverage and Integration Salzburg	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	
Flüchtlingskoordination Tirol, Tiroler Sozialer Dienst Refugee Coordination Tyrol, Social Services Tyrol	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	
Abteilung Gesellschaft, Soziales und Integration Vorarlberg Department for Society, Social Affairs and Integration Vorarlberg, Caritas Vorarlberg	Provincial	Executive body	Reception/ Integration	

Annex III: Flow chart of the national reception system

Source: Own design.

Annex IV: Flow chart of the Austrian asylum procedure

Source: AIDA, Asylum Information Database, Country Report Austria 2016 (update 2017), p. 15, available at <http://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/austria>

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